

Sr. No. DBRANLU/NC/ONOE/2025/

DR. B.R. AMBEDKAR NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, SONEPAT

CERTIFICATE OF PRESENTATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar

For presenting a paper on *Synchronising Elections in India: A Comparative Study of Constitutional, Federal and Democratic Challenges* in the National Conference on **One Nation, One Election: Constitutional, Federal, and Democratic Dimensions** held on 6th & 7th September, 2025 at Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University, Sonapat

Prof. (Dr.) Ashutosh Mishra

REGISTRAR & DEAN ACADEMIC AFFAIRS

DBRANLU, SONEPAT

Prof. (Dr.) Devinder Singh

HON'BLE VICE CHANCELLOR

DBRANLU, SONEPAT

TABLE OF CONTENTS

HISTORICAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL CONTEXT

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: RETHINKING FEDERALISM AND ELECTORAL REFORM IN INDIA	19
Dr. Vibhuti Nakta & Madhav Singh Mogha	
CONSTITUTIONAL PATHWAYS TO ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: BALANCING FEDERALISM AND DEMOCRATIC REFORM	20
Ms. Shruti Tandon & Mr. Sachin	
OVERSIGHT OR INTENT? CONSTITUENT ASSEMBLY DEBATES AND THE ABSENCE OF A SYNCHRONISED ELECTION CLAUSE	21
Eram Sadaf	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: TRACING HISTORICAL ROOTS AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS IN INDIA'S DEMOCRATIC FRAMEWORK	23
Kartikay Pawar	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL, AND DEMOCRATIC DIMENSIONS	24
Prachi Chande	
SYNCHRONIZING THE BALLOT: UNPACKING 'ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION' AND ITS RIPPLE EFFECTS ON INDIA'S CONSTITUTIONAL HARMONY AND DEMOCRATIC FABRIC	25
Vaibhav Singh & Nikesh Narendra Nakshane	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION	26
Amrit Kaur & Harshita Chahar	
A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF ONE NATION ONE ELECTION FROM THE GRUND-NORM	27
Tanishka Goel	

LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS

CONCEPT OF ‘ONE NATION ONE ELECTION’ AND ITS ADHERENCE TO CONSTITUTIONAL MANDATES & SILENCES	30
Nyayverdhan Singh	
ONE NATION ONE ELECTION- LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS	31
Nisha Sharma	
SYNCHRONISING DEMOCRACY: CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES AND POSSIBILITIES OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION	32
Adv. Keerthana Krishnan	
SYNCHRONIZING INDIAN ELECTIONS: LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION	33
Jinesh M	
CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION IN INDIA	35
Mayank Chandra & Siddhika Sharma	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION- CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL, AND DEMOCRATIC DIMENSIONS LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS	36
Rukmini Ravi Madhok	
REFORM OF ELECTORAL SYNCHRONISATION WITH THE CONSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF COOPERATIVE FEDERALISM	38
Devesh Kumar	
UNIFIED POLLS, DIVIDED OPINIONS: ANALYZING THE CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL AND LEGAL DIMENSIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION	39
Ishita Chawla & Agreema Justa	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION AND THE FATE OF THE NO-CONFIDENCE MOTION: CONSTITUTIONAL ACCOUNTABILITY AT THE CROSSROADS	41
Adeeb Bakhtawar & Mohd. Zeeshan	

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A CONSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS OF LEGAL ISSUES AND THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE	43
Anvi Meena	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: SYNCHRONY OR STRAIN ON INDIA'S CONSTITUTIONAL FABRIC?	44
Manya Gupta & Aditi Tripathi	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: CONSTITUTIONAL FEASIBILITY AND FEDERAL CHALLENGES	46
Khusboo Poonia & Adhyan Singh	
CONSTITUTIONAL CONTOURS OF 'ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION': LEGAL CHALLENGES AND FEDERAL IMPLICATIONS	47
Abhay Bidua & Harsh Jajam	
ANALYSING THE CONSTITUTIONAL VALIDITY OF 'ONE NATION ONE ELECTION'	49
Arunika Paul Nandi	
ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: EXPLORING LEGAL, CONSTITUTIONAL AND ECONOMIC DIMENSIONS	50
Rohini Singh & Prachi Sharma	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS IN CONTEMPORARY INDIA	52
Mohit Sangwan & Vaishnavi	
SYNCHRONICITY AT THE COST OF SOVEREIGNTY: A CRITICAL EXAMINATION OF 'ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION' AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIA'S FEDERAL STRUCTURE	53
Krishna Pratap Patel & Kanishka Garg	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A BANE OR A BOON?	54
Shaurya Pratap Singh & Adarsh Kumar	

POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS

POLITICAL PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN: A STUDY IN THE CONTEXT OF PUNJAB AND HARYANA	57
Dr. Suman & Dr. Jai Prakash	
REGIONAL VOICES IN A NATIONAL NARRATIVE: THE POLITICAL CONSEQUENCES OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION	57
Ritu Tyagi & Divyanshu Lakwad	
DEMOCRACY IN TANDEM: POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS OF SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS IN INDIA	59
Raman Goyal & Rohan Tyagi	
ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION AND THE FUTURE OF COALITION POLITICS	60
Abhaydeep Singh	
HARMONIZING ELECTORAL CYCLES: POLITICAL CENTRALIZATION AND GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES IN INDIA'S ONE NATION ONE ELECTION FRAMEWORK	61
Yash Chandan	
POLITICAL STABILITY THROUGH ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A MYTH OR A SUSTAINABLE REALITY?	63
Purva Mehta & Sidharth Rathore	
ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATION FOR INDIA.	64
Rudra Dhawan & Navin Dudi	
THE DEMOCRATIC DILEMMA OF SYNCHRONISED ELECTIONS	66
Vinayak Parashar & Sachin Yadav	
CRITICS OF ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: A CONSTITUTIONAL AND DEMOCRATIC APPRAISAL	67
Shiwani	

**ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS
IN INDIA'S FEDERAL DEMOCRACY 68**

Arshika Dahiya & Deepanshu

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION- A CRITICAL INQUIRY 69

Vanshaj Bhardwaj & Mayank Sharma

ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS

**SYNCHRONIZING DEMOCRACY: ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC
DIMENSIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION IN INDIA 73**

Manvi Singh

ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC STAKES OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION 75

Apoorv Mishra & Madhav Monga

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: A MUCH-NEEDED REFORM? 76

Ankur Taya

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: ANALYSING ADMINISTRATIVE CONSTRAINT 77

Bhavya Kapil

**ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF ELECTORAL
SYNCHRONIZATION IN THE WORLD'S LARGEST DEMOCRACY. 78**

Swaraj Dash

**THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF DEMOCRACY: ENVIRONMENTAL ECONOMICS
OF ELECTORAL CYCLES 79**

Khushbu Yadav

**THE COST OF DEMOCRACY: ADMINISTRATIVE AND FINANCIAL DIMENSIONS
OF ELECTIONS IN INDIA 81**

Mritunjay Kumar Mishra

**ONE NATION ONE ELECTION IN INDIA: NAVIGATING THROUGH
ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC CHALLENGES 82**

Navin Pal Singh

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION 83

Aditya Sahu & Akshit Broka

**ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE
ELECTION: TOWARDS ENHANCED GOVERNANCE AND FISCAL EFFICIENCY 84**

Vinay Kumar Lakhlan & Diksha Kumari

VOTER ENGAGEMENT AND DEMOCRATIC PARTICIPATION

**ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: AN AGENDA FOR ELECTORAL REFORMS IN
INDIA 87**

Nisha & Lakshay

**THE SILENT CONSTITUENCY: WHY STUDENTS MUST BE CENTRAL TO THE
ONOE DEBATE 88**

Somesh Rai

**ELECTORAL CONTINUITY AND STABILITY VS. VOTER AUTONOMY:
DOCTRINAL CONFLICTS IN THE ONOE DEBATE 89**

Ishita Jawla & Vaibhav Khanna

**A CRITICAL RESEARCH REVIEW ON THE POTENTIAL IMPACT OF ONE NATION
AND ONE ELECTION: THE VOTER'S PERSPECTIVE 90**

Ishita Anand

**PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACTS OF ELECTORAL SYNCHRONIZATION ON VOTER
BEHAVIOUR 91**

Piyush & Saksham Singh

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION WITH INCLUSIVE PARTICIPATION 93

Pragya

**UNIFORMITY AT WHAT COST? RETHINKING ELECTORAL REFORM AMIDST
FEDERALISM AND INSTITUTIONAL TRUST DEFICITS 94**

Mehak Marodia

ONE NATION AND ONE ELECTION 95

Akhil Chauhan & Priyanshu Chunboug

**THE HEGEMONY OF SYNCHRONY: EVM FRAGILITY, FEDERAL FAULTLINES,
AND INDIA'S RISK OF DOMESTIC COLD WAR UNDER ONOE 97**

Anup Kumar Yadav & Harsh Srivastava

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION 98

Radhika Chawla & Varma Khushi

COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES

**SYNCHRONIZING ELECTIONS IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF
CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL, AND DEMOCRATIC CHALLENGES 101**

Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar

**REVISITING SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ONE
NATION, ONE ELECTION AND GLOBAL ELECTORAL MODELS 103**

Vikas Man Singh & Radha

**CONSTITUTIONAL VIABILITY OF ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: COMPARATIVE
STUDY WITH FEDERAL DEMOCRACIES AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN INDIA 105**

Srishty & Pinky Bansal

**UNLOCKING INDIA'S POTENTIAL: THE PROS AND CONS OF 'SIMULTANEOUS
ELECTION' 106**

Harsh Raj & Prakash Kumar Patel

**DEMOCRATIC ENGAGEMENT IN THE AGE OF ELECTORAL
SYNCHRONIZATION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RISKS AND REFORMS 107**

Havish Dhanwantri & Veni Arora

**SYNCHRONIZING ELECTIONS IN INDIA: LESSONS FROM HISTORY AND
EUROPE FOR TODAY'S POLITICAL LANDSCAPE 108**

Puja & Radhika Aggarwal

**FEASIBILITIES OF SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE
STUDY ON DEMOCRACIES 110**

Akshat & Lalit Kumar

HISTORICAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL CONTEXT

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: RETHINKING FEDERALISM AND ELECTORAL REFORM IN INDIA

Dr. Vibhuti Nakta¹ & Madhav Singh Mogha²

The proposal of “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) has emerged as a critical reform debate in Indian democracy. It seeks to hold simultaneous elections for the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies with the promise of reducing electoral expenditure, curbing policy paralysis caused by repeated enforcement of the Model Code of Conduct, and improving governance efficiency. Historically, India conducted synchronized elections between 1951 and 1967, but political realignments, premature dissolutions, and the growing role of regional parties disrupted this cycle. Revisiting the model raises complex constitutional, political, and federal questions. This paper draws lessons from the past, analyses the challenges ONOE poses to India’s federal structure and democratic diversity, and identifies potential pathways for reform. It also includes a comparative analysis with other countries with one nation and one election to provide a global perspective on the implementation and outcomes of such systems. It argues that while synchronized elections could streamline governance, they must not undermine state autonomy or the federal spirit enshrined in the Constitution. A phased synchronization model, backed by legal safeguards, institutional strengthening, and cooperative consensus-building, offers a balanced route for the future of electoral reform in India.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election; Simultaneous Elections; Federalism; Indian Constitution; Electoral Reform; Governance; Democracy; State Autonomy.*

¹ Ph. D. Scholar, *Panjab University.*

² Student, *Panjab University.*

CONSTITUTIONAL PATHWAYS TO ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: BALANCING FEDERALISM AND DEMOCRATIC REFORM

Ms. Shruti Tandon³ & Mr. Sachin⁴

“The Constitution is a living document.”

This seminal affirmation by the Supreme Court in the locus classicus case of *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973) epitomizes the dynamic and evolving nature of constitutional jurisprudence in India, urging continual adaptation to meet the demands of a complex and changing polity. Anchored in this transformative vision, the present study undertakes a nuanced examination of electoral synchronisation—popularly encapsulated as “One Nation, One Election”—as a constitutional innovation. It probes the intricate balance between preserving the foundational values of federalism and parliamentary democracy, and embracing strategic reform through evolutionary interpretation and principled constitutional design. By recognizing the Constitution not merely as a static text but as an enduring framework capable of progressive transformation, this research critically explores pathways to reconcile administrative coherence with democratic pluralism within India’s federal structure.

While existing analyses often focus on the administrative merits or constitutional constraints of electoral synchronisation, there remains a significant gap in exploring how innovative constitutional reforms and interpretive strategies can reconcile these dimensions without compromising foundational democratic principles. This study addresses the problem of how the Constitution (129th Amendment) Bill, 2024 can be substantively strengthened to enable electoral harmonisation that respects federal autonomy, safeguards parliamentary accountability, and upholds institutional integrity.

³ Junior Research Fellow & Ph.D. Scholar, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University*.

⁴ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University*.

Drawing upon the doctrines of basic structure and constitutional morality, and informed by comparative federalism models, the research identifies key deficiencies in the current amendment framework—such as the ambiguous discretionary powers conferred and lack of explicit safeguards for electoral timelines—and proposes reforms including judicial oversight mechanisms, constitutionally mandated criteria for election deferments, graded implementation phases, and voluntary state participation pathways. This constitutional evolution, grounded in living constitutionalism principles, promises to balance efficiency in electoral administration with deep respect for India’s federal democratic ethos. The paper outlines a path for reform that harmonizes administrative efficiency with constitutional fidelity, fostering democratic consensus through principled amendment and interpretative innovation.

Keywords: *Electoral Synchronisation, Constitutional Amendment, Living Constitution, Basic Structure, Democratic Federalism, Institutional Design.*

OVERSIGHT OR INTENT? CONSTITUENT ASSEMBLY DEBATES AND THE ABSENCE OF A SYNCHRONISED ELECTION CLAUSE

Eram Sadaf⁵

The ongoing discussion about One Nation, One Election (ONOE) has brought to light questions of efficiency, governance stability, and cost reduction. Yet, a deeper constitutional silence often goes unexamined: the Constituent Assembly Debates did not incorporate any explicit provision mandating synchronised elections across Union and State legislatures. The problem emerges because while Articles 83, 172, and 324 thoroughly outline aspects like tenure, dissolution, and electoral authority, they don’t address the topic of electoral synchronization. Scholars have extensively documented the concerns of the framers regarding the balance between centralization and state, yet the lack of discussion on synchronization is still not well-explored. Advocates for ONOE view this gap as something that needs to be fixed, while historical records might indicate

⁵ Student, *Patna Women’s College.*

that this silence was actually a deliberate choice. Thus, this research explores three interrelated questions: How did the framers envision tenure, dissolution, and electoral cycles, and what does their lack of discussion on synchronization tell us about their constitutional intentions? How does this silence shape the federal bargain between uniformity and flexibility? And what comparative lessons emerge from federations such as Canada and Germany, where staggered electoral cycles are institutionalised as safeguards against central dominance? This research takes a qualitative interpretive approach, diving deep into the Constituent Assembly Debates. It closely examines the contributions of key figures like Ambedkar, Alladi Krishnaswami Ayyar, and K.T. Shah to piece together the reasoning of the framers. Additionally, it analyzes constitutional provisions related to tenure and dissolution and compares India's model with other federations that use staggered cycles as a way to enhance democracy. Tentative findings suggest that: The lack of discussion around synchronization appears to be a purposeful constitutional strategy, not just an oversight. This approach ensures that staggered elections keep local and regional issues at the forefront of political discussions, rather than merging them into a one-size-fits-all national contest. These staggered cycles also allow for varied political mandates, giving citizens the chance to express different preferences at both national and state levels, which in turn strengthens our multi-tiered democracy. Importantly, this design implicitly challenges the notion of uniformity, acknowledging that synchronization could lead to a central dominance that undermines state autonomy within the Union. A comparative analysis further supports this view: countries like Canada and Germany, by opting for staggered elections, show that desynchronization is not a sign of inefficiency but a strategic institutional choice aimed at preserving pluralism, decentralization, and various forms of political accountability. Thus, the debate on ONOE must be understood not just as a simple administrative change, but as a significant shift in our constitutional framework. A change that risks to disrupt the original vision of a flexible, federal, and multi-layered democratic system that the framers intended.

Keywords: *Constituent Assembly Debates, Democratic Responsiveness, Federalism, One Nation One Election, Synchronised Electoral Cycles.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: TRACING HISTORICAL ROOTS AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS IN INDIA'S DEMOCRATIC FRAMEWORK

Kartikay Pawar⁶

India's overture for the simultaneous elections better known as "One Nation, One Election" in simple language means the conduct of elections of all the three tiers of the constitutional institutions which are House of the People (Lok Sabha), State assemblies (Vidhan Sabha) and Local bodies taking place in unison is an intermittent dialogue since independence of the Nation.

India's expedition with respect to hands on democracy took place in the year 1951-1952, where a vast figure of voters assembled to cast their first vote which reflected the will of the people. The choosing to Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies were held concomitantly till the fourth election, which took place in the year 1967 but after this voting between the different organs were not taking place concurrently off the back of disturb in the year 1968 and 1969 off the back of preterm cessation of some state Legislative assemblies.

Over the past decade, Nation is wrestling with the same dilemma with hundreds of state assembly election come to pass. The governing board in the year 2023 headed by the former President discussed the reasonableness of conducting the simultaneous election.

The main reason and the need of the art to incorporate this theory is to minimize the frequency of elections which are taking place in our country which in conclusion will help to save a huge cost which is required in conducting of the elections and prone to disruptions to governance which will help to improve overall administration.

This paper will help in tracing the historical roots of the contemporaneous election and the constitutional dimensions which are associated in order to produce contemporaneous elections

⁶ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

which is the point of debate for the period of time and it comes to a close with digest perception and put forward exhortation for a guarded approach to implement One Nation, One Election with upholding the democratic foundations and federal justness.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Simultaneous elections, Historical, Constitutional.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL, AND DEMOCRATIC DIMENSIONS

*Prachi Chande*⁷

"Democracy' and 'free and fair election' are inseparable. Elections are the centerpiece of democracy; it is difficult to visualize democracy without elections. Ensuring free and fair elections is the first prerequisite for the success of democratic process. Elections are a very vital part of the political process which emanates from the fundamental assumption that people are sovereign. In any democracy, the people do want and have every right to change governments according to their wishes, in a peaceful and orderly manner. The little man, in his multitude, making his vote at the poll does a social audit of his Parliament plus political choice of his proxy. Elections give the executive and legislative branches the representative nature they need to reflect the will of the people. The most powerful aspect of democracy unquestionably is the highest number of individuals participating in elections. A constitution needs to be a living constitution to endure the tides of time and adapt to the changing requirement of generations . However at the same time there are some intrinsic values , a basic framework on which the whole content of the constitution rests . This framework originalism is the very essence of the legal system which the constitution documents embodies and which the courts try to protect through their various doctrines and pronouncements. This Indian constitution is undoubtedly an organic constitution and has successfully responded to the charging needs of the society.

Keywords: *Constitution, Election, Governments, Individual, Democracy*

⁷ Student, *St. Xavier's University Newtown Kolkata*

SYNCHRONIZING THE BALLOT: UNPACKING 'ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION' AND ITS RIPPLE EFFECTS ON INDIA'S CONSTITUTIONAL HARMONY AND DEMOCRATIC FABRIC

Vaibhav Singh⁸ & Nikesh Narendra Nakshane⁹

The concept of "one nation, one election" (ONOE) is touted as a clever solution to India's increasing election expenditure—more than ₹60,000 crore in 2019—and the strain of round-the-clock polling. At first blush, it guarantees efficiency and respite for both the administration and the voters. But closer examination reveals that ONOE is more than saving money or matters of logistics—it would redefine the pillars of India's democracy.

India did conduct simultaneous elections between 1951 and 1967, but that broke down as soon as state legislatures were prematurely dissolved and coalition politics began. To introduce it now would involve fundamental changes to the constitution, such as amending articles 83 and 172, reduced terms for mid-cycle-dissolved assemblies, and additional powers for the election commission of India (ECI). These would make parliament's accountability tools—such as the no-confidence motion—less effective and leave the ECI more vulnerable to political influence.

ONOE also has federal implications. By circumventing the states in making crucial decisions, it could overshadow local issues with national campaigns. Studies even reveal that when elections are conducted concurrently, voters vote predominantly for the same party at both state and national levels, narrowing room for regional voices.

Thus, though ONOE may save costs and simplify administration, it has serious pay-offs: reduced accountability, increased concentration of power, diminished federalism, and fewer arenas for state interests. The question is not merely one of efficiency—it's one of whether India is ready to give up democratic diversity at the altar of convenience.

⁸ Student, *Bharati Vidyapeeth New law college Pune Maharashtra.*

⁹ Student, *Bharati Vidyapeeth New law college Pune Maharashtra.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION

Amrit Kaur¹⁰ & Harshita Chahar¹¹

The proposal of “One Nation, One Election” has created a debate in India’s political negotiations, promising to improve the country’s democratic processes. The idea aims to synchronize the elections of the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies and lower level within 100 days. The proposal is often advocated on grounds of administrative efficiency, reduction of expenditure. Understanding these concepts is important to evaluating whether such reform is viable in India’s federal structure. India initiated its democratic journey with simultaneous elections. From 1951 to 1967, simultaneous elections were conducted in India. This order was shaken due to political instability and premature dissolutions of assemblies. The governments were dismissed under Article 356. From then until now India followed the concept of irregular elections.

With benefits, there comes a lot of challenges constitutionally for synchronizing elections. The terms of the Lok Sabha and State Assemblies are governed by Articles 83 and 172 of the Constitution, which prescribe a maximum duration of five years, unless dissolved earlier. Adjusting the electoral process would require either extending or mutilating the tenure of some legislatures, raising questions over democracy. Moreover, it highlights the tension between centre and state concerning federalism. This paper highlights the debate between both the historical and constitutional framework of India. By analysing why the idea of simultaneous elections was disrupted and assesses if current conditions such as coalition politics, regional parties, and federal complications would allow its introduction. The paper argues the demand and cautions. The research shows that “One Nation, One Election” is not only a political but constitutional and historical question. Any attempt to implement it must not undermine the values of democracy and constitution.

¹⁰ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

¹¹ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF ONE NATION ONE ELECTION FROM THE GRUND-NORM

Tanishka Goel¹²

The proposal of One Nation One Election proposes the idea of simultaneous elections in the Lok Sabha and the State Legislative assemblies, as well as the Panchayat and the Municipal Corporations in two different phases. In recent years, this idea has garnered a lot of political and academic attention. This paper critically analyzes the constitutional and historical legitimacy of this notion in the context of Indian democracy. The research follows the roots of simultaneous elections back to the initial years of the Republic, when all the first four general elections (1951–1967) were held together. Nevertheless, because of premature dissolution of a number of State Assemblies and the Lok Sabha, synchronization was broken. The study examines the background of the turn, examining whether the move towards a single electoral cycle is consistent with constitutional provisions and democratic practices.

In addition, the paper examines the constitutional aspects of the concept by evaluating applicable Articles of the constitution, including Articles 83, 172, 356, and 368, to check if such a reform can be adopted without infringing federal autonomy or the basic structure doctrine. Major decisions of the Supreme Court and suggestions from Law Commissions and Parliamentary Committees are analysed as well.

The paper further reflects on possible constitutional amendments needed to enact the reform, as well as pragmatic issues regarding logistics, political consensus, and electoral equality. Although supporters claim that simultaneous elections will save money, minimize policy interruption, and decrease administrative machinery burdens, critics suggest that it would concentrate power and dilute regional representation.

¹² Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University*.

Finally, the paper reaches the conclusion that even though One Nation, One Election has had a history in the country, its realization at the constitutional level must be approached with a delicate balancing of democratic norms, federal nature, and election integrity. It promotes a consultative process with all stakeholders to examine its feasibility within India's pluralistic environment.

Keywords: *Simultaneous elections, Constitutional Validity, History, Federalism, Indian Constitution.*

LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS

CONCEPT OF 'ONE NATION ONE ELECTION' AND ITS ADHERENCE TO CONSTITUTIONAL MANDATES & SILENCES

Nyayverdhan Singh¹³

The concept of 'one nation one election' was brought into discussion to assure that the elections of all three tiers could be conducted simultaneously. Although the concept 'one Nation one election' sounds futuristic and public welfare oriented, it is full of anomalies. The concept of 'one nation one election' fails to fulfil mandates of constitutional silences. The policy of 'one nation one election' failed to entail into its ambit key public-spirited concepts like transparency, accountability, good governance, fairness and public welfare. The key reason claimed to enforce 'one nation one election' is the financial burden of contesting the elections regularly, but this cannot be forgotten that in a democratic country like India what other more important work do we have for which money is required to be saved other than elections. The sense/support for a government can change at any moment and the will of people shall need to be respected in terms of change of government and thus contesting elections at different times (whenever necessary) is one such significant feature of Indian democracy. We can't afford to lose/sacrifice the constitutional mandate of contesting elections just for the sake of saving the money in terms of reducing financial burden. Election forms the soul of the democratic process and there exists nothing more important work than to conduct elections. What major focus shall be, is to conduct the elections in a more accurate, accountable and transparent manner so that the people of India can feel and sense their participation in the election process. If the process of conducting an election will not be user friendly, transparent and accountable to the public, the purpose of conducting an election is defeated for the fact that the public casting its vote will not be able to verify it and the government in opposition having doubts about conducting unfair elections will persist. Practically, the people of india are not the stakeholders in the conduct of the elections contested throughout the nation for the fact that the elections are conducted out of public money

¹³ Research Scholar, *South Asian University*.

whereas public involvement was kept minimal with the excuse that the election processes are confidential. So far, public involvement of those who are taxpayers, as stakeholder, in the election conducting process is that of an indemnifier and for those who don't pay taxes are bound to accept the role of devotee of the election conduction process. Thus, instead of saving the money in the name of concept 'one nation one election', a wider and more relevant problem needs to be resolved.

Through this study, it was tried to obtain the presumed outcome that the concept of 'one nation one election' was not in public good and requires substantial modification. The Study performed is doctrinal with the technique used is analysis, description and comparative Discussion.

Keywords: *constitutional silences; financial burden; one nation one election; Simultaneously; stakeholder.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION- LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS

Nisha Sharma¹⁴

The concept of One Nation, One Election has come to the fore as a significant reform initiative in India, aiming to align elections for the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. The idea of concurrent elections for all levels of government has been a subject of wrangle and has accumulated attention as a potential reform to rationalize the electoral process and shorten the thrust of frequent polls on governance and resources. The principle attention behind this design is to enhance administrative coherence, cut down election management costs, and terminate recurring elections from happening very often. This idea may seem to be very pragmatic on the surface, but it brings a lot of constitutional and legal defiance. The main concerns are the effect on the Federal structure of India, Representative Democracy and Free and fair elections. The research paper shall outline the historical background and philosophy behind the 'One Nation,

¹⁴ Ph. D Scholar, *TERI School of Advanced Studies.*

One Election' proposal, sketching the key constitutional provisions, debates, and learning insights. It scrutinizes the constitutional provisions that command elections in India, emphasizing the essence of federalism and the democratic principles enshrined in the Constitution. Furthermore, this paper explores the challenges and potential benefits of implementing simultaneous elections, encompassing constitutional, political, logistical, and administrative aspects. It also assesses the impact on regional parties, the federal structure, and the representation of diverse voices in the democratic process. Proper respect must be given to constitutional limits, and must make sure that the democratic ethos of our country is not compromised. A phased and carefully regulated framework is essential to synchronise elections without compromising on the principles of federalism and representative democracy. The study also addresses concerns about the constitutional implications of extending or curtailing the tenure of certain elected bodies to synchronize elections, as well as possible adjustments to electoral laws and constitutional amendments to facilitate the reform.

SYNCHRONISING DEMOCRACY: CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES AND POSSIBILITIES OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION

Adv. Keerthana Krishnan¹⁵

The concept of One Nation, One Election (ONOE) has surfaced as one of the most contentious constitutional reforms in modern India, prompting discussions about its legal viability, the balance of federalism, and its democratic legitimacy. Although simultaneous elections were standard in the initial years of the Republic, political and constitutional changes after 1967 disrupted this tradition, resulting in staggered electoral cycles. Therefore, reviving ONOE necessitates more than just administrative coordination; it requires thorough constitutional examination. This Article, titled "Synchronising Democracy: Constitutional Challenges and Possibilities of One Nation, One Election," conducts a doctrinal legal analysis of the constitutional framework that governs elections in India. The approach is strictly doctrinal,

¹⁵ Student, *Calicut University*.

depending on constitutional provisions (notably Articles 83, 85, 172, 174, 324–329), the Representation of People Acts, judicial precedents, reports from the Law Commission and Election Commission, as well as academic literature. The research does not take an empirical field approach but instead assesses the matter within the constitutional text, structure, and principles such as democracy, federalism, and the basic structure doctrine. The paper contends that while ONOE could potentially improve stability, decrease electoral costs, and enhance governance, it also presents significant constitutional challenges most prominently the diminishment of State autonomy, disruption of the federal equilibrium, and the danger of compromising the democratic principle of accountability through frequent elections. By engaging with comparative constitutional experiences and evaluating ONOE against the basic structure doctrine, the study emphasizes that the proposal is not inherently unconstitutional; however, its execution would necessitate careful constitutional amendments and protective measures. The preliminary conclusion drawn is that ONOE, while normatively beneficial for democratic synchronization, can only be achieved through a phased and meticulously crafted reform that honors India's federal nature and constitutional ethics. Instead of a complete transformation, a gradual synchronization approach, bolstered by strong constitutional frameworks, presents a more feasible route.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Constitutional Challenges, Federalism, Basic Structure Doctrine, Electoral Reform.*

SYNCHRONIZING INDIAN ELECTIONS: LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION

Jinesh M¹⁶

The idea behind One Nation, One Election is all about the possibility of holding elections for the Lok Sabha and all State legislatures at the same time, and maybe even for local bodies too. The

¹⁶ Student, *School of LawVistas, Chennai, VISTAS, Chennai.*

goal is to make governance smoother, cut down on election costs, and promote political stability. However, when we look at the legal and constitutional aspects, this kind of reform brings both significant benefits and serious challenges to India's democratic framework and federal structure.

For simultaneous elections to happen, we would need to make major changes to the Constitution, especially concerning the terms and dissolution of legislative bodies as outlined in Articles 83, 172, and the newly suggested Article 82A. Right now, individual state assemblies and Parliament have their own terms and dissolution processes, which helps maintain federalism through separate electoral cycles. Changing these timelines could lead to worries about too much centralization and might infringe on state autonomy, a fundamental principle safeguarded by the Constitution's basic structure doctrine, as highlighted in the *Kesavananda Bharati* case.

India's federal system is all about the balance between central and state governments, each with its own set of powers. The One Nation, One Election proposal could blur this line by merging national and state electoral issues into one timeline. This might result in political issues becoming too uniform, reducing attention to state-specific matters and threatening the rich diversity that defines Indian democracy. To align terms, we might have to make arbitrary changes to the lengths of legislative bodies, which could undermine democratic principles and the essence of cooperative federalism.

From a democratic perspective, holding elections at the same time is expected to boost voter turnout, reduce election fatigue, and make better use of administrative and security resources. On the flip side, critics warn that this synchronization might dilute the representation of local interests and elevate national issues, which could undermine the vibrancy and diversity of our democracy. It may also limit the visibility of local parties and stifle the expression of regional identities in electoral discussions.

Legal considerations highlight the importance of achieving broad consensus, drafting legislation carefully, and implementing strong procedural safeguards. Reports from the Law Commission (170th, 255th) and recommendations from NITI Aayog point out the logistical and legal challenges involved, such as the need to amend several constitutional articles, synchronize

different state election cycles, and ensure smooth governance during transition periods. Any effective legal reform must respect the principles of the Constitution, uphold electoral fairness, and ensure that changes do not compromise the fundamental structure or democratic values.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Constitutional Amendments, Federalism, State Autonomy, Democratic Governance.*

CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION IN INDIA

Mayank Chandra¹⁷ & Siddhika Sharma¹⁸

This paper discusses the constitutional impediments faced by all three organs of the world's largest democratic country. Since the NDA led by BJP and Shri Narendra Modi as Prime Minister came into power in the year 2014 they constantly articulate on the topic of "One Nation One Election". BJP even included this topic as a key point in their election manifestos of 2019 as well as of 2024, that clearly manifest the significant interest regarding the same. But "The proposition of 'One Nation, One Election' resonates as an appealing and transformative electoral reform, promising lucidity, efficiency, and reduction of governance disruptions; however, its practical understanding encounters arduous constitutional, federal, logistical, and political impediments that requires critical examination." Application of 'One Nation, One Election' in world largest democracy which operates on world longest written constitution requires major constitutional amendments on Articles governing duration and dissolution of legislature which are Article 83, Article 85, Article 172, Article 174, and this articles can only be amended in parliament by special majority with ratification of at least half of states legislatures. From the Executive perspective, the proposal is accompanied by both advantages and challenges. Even though the enforcement is hesitant in the 1.5 billion-plus populated country, the expected benefits in reduced financial costs, saved administrative efforts, and the efficiency improvements

¹⁷ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

¹⁸ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

necessitate a hunch look, but prudently. As far as the judiciary is concerned, it will be critical in evaluating the constitutional validity of the proposal in the light of known tenets like the basic structure doctrine, the separation of powers, and the federal nature of the Constitution. This research aims to understand the complex challenges related to the proposal of 'One Nation, One Election' through an in-depth methodological approach. The research is done on the basis of publicly available documents of governmental as well as private institutions. Along with that, it is also based on data from different time periods, formatted interviews, and the well-thought opinions of experts, all of which have been of great importance while doing the analysis and coming to conclusions.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Constitutional Validity, Basic Structure Doctrine, Federalism, Separation of Powers, Democratic Representation, Electoral reforms, Legislative Amendments, Election Commission of India, Electoral Reform, Constitutional Amendments, Judicial Review*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION- CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL, AND DEMOCRATIC DIMENSIONS LEGAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS

Rukmini Ravi Madhok¹⁹

Free and fair elections are the cornerstone of any successful democratic society. It has been one of the basic and most important freedoms envisioned by our constitution makers while separating India from the colonial rule. Free and fair elections on a federal level allow issues from a grassroots level to be heard with adept importance. The idea of 'One Nation, One Election has come up to be a significant issue with the rise of the Modi Government. The people who support this model argue that frequent elections often burden the government and disrupt governance due to the reoccurring elections. The advocates of this policy say that it would be helpful to reduce

¹⁹ Student, *Jindal Global Law School*.

the fiscal and administrative burden on the government while also ensuring policy continuity. However, in the large democracy that is India, this idea comes with its own set of constitutional, federal and democratic complexities.

On a constitutional level, implementing One Nation, One Election would call for altering the basic structure of the constitution and thus making significant amendments to the current framework. This would include amending the tenure of legislative bodies, the emergency powers and laws related to elections. Such changes are of extremely delicate nature and can risk altering the very foundation on which the roles of the legislature and executive are built. It points towards a change at the core of the parliamentary framework.

On a federal level, the states would fear losing their autonomous rights. Elections would be decided by a central electoral schedule which would diminish flexibility of the state governments. It undermines the spirit of cooperative federal structure that our constitution enshrines. Moreover, One Nation, One Election would homogenize issues at a central level and would dilute the importance of state specific concerns. This would threaten bringing a uniform veil over the diverse state specific challenges India poses.

On a democratic level, One Nation, One Election risks losing accountability of the governments. While the concept is resource intensive, it does not take into account the fact that frequent elections force governments at every level to listen and resolve issues put forth by the public. The responsiveness of the government can be reduced to a drastic level if we envision a single central election.

My paper shall contain a detailed examination on the constitutional amendments required to implement such a vast change, the federal implications on the autonomy of states and an analysis of the democratic exchanges between efficiency and representation especially in a diverse and large country such as India. The paper shall also include phase implementation strategies such as a two-phase election process in order to make sure that the transition to a single election, if done, is done in a smooth and balanced manner.

REFORM OF ELECTORAL SYNCHRONISATION WITH THE CONSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF COOPERATIVE FEDERALISM

Devesh Kumar²⁰

The One Nation One Election (ONOE) initiative proposes synchronising elections for the Lok Sabha and state legislative assemblies in India. This paper evaluates the feasibility and effectiveness of ONOE by examining constitutional challenges and the implications for cooperative federalism. It reviews relevant constitutional provisions governing electoral cycles, specifically Articles 83, 172, 324, 356, and 368, and identifies the legal and judicial obstacles to aligning assembly and parliamentary elections. The paper emphasises the necessity of constitutional amendments, judicial oversight, and intergovernmental cooperation, and at the same time, the administrative and financial considerations that are to be addressed with particular attention to the logistical requirements of conducting simultaneous elections for over 900 million voters. The findings of the paper highlight that enhanced Election Commission capacity, technological advancements, and coordinated planning could improve resource allocation and reduce costs associated with elections. The paper critically assesses the effects of ONOE on voter behaviour, regional party dynamics, and the federal structure while ONOE has the potential to decrease voter fatigue and promote governance stability but at the same time it may also diminish the prominence of local issues and concentrate political power at the centre. The paper also conducts a comparative analysis of federal democracies, including the United States, Germany, and Australia, which can offer additional perspectives for addressing these challenges. The author employs the method of comparative analysis of legal documents, research papers, books, and official government websites for sources to investigate the origin, nature, potential developments, and challenges in implementation associated with the One Nation One Election process. The outcome of this paper will conclude with policy recommendations, a phased implementation strategy, legal reforms, administrative improvements, and measures to safeguard

²⁰ Student, *Himachal Pradesh National Law University*.

democratic processes. Overall, ONOE is identified as a viable reform with the potential to enhance the efficiency, participation, and legitimacy of India's electoral system, demonstrating that the Constitution of India is a living document, and changes to it are to be made over time to keep it relevant. However, while making these changes, we must keep the spirit of the basic structure doctrine in mind.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election (ONOE); Synchronized Elections; Conflict of Interest (COI); Federalism; Simultaneous Elections; Voter's Behaviour.*

UNIFIED POLLS, DIVIDED OPINIONS: ANALYZING THE CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL AND LEGAL DIMENSIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION

Ishita Chawla²¹ & Agreema Justa²²

The disquisition on “One Nation, One Election” has assumed prominence in the political and constitutional paradigms of contemporary India. Intrinsicly, this proposal seeks to synchronize elections to the House of People and the State Legislative Assemblies, so that citizens cast their votes for both levels of government simultaneously, thereby ensuring that both are conducted at the same time within a common electoral cycle. India, being the world's largest democracy, conducts elections on an unparalleled scale and engages millions of voters across an electorate spanning varied social, cultural and regional milieus. The discourse on ONOE concerns the very architecture of Indian democracy, positioning itself as an antidote to the perpetual cycle of elections. To operationalize this vision, the 129th Constitutional Amendment Bill, 2024 proposes the insertion of Article 82-A and consequential modifications to Articles 83, 172, and 327. The bill has been referred to a Joint Parliamentary Committee for further scrutiny.

²¹ Student, *University Institute of Legal Studies, Panjab University.*

²² Student, *University Institute of Legal Studies, Panjab University.*

Viewed through a legal prism, it safeguards the constitutional ethos of federal synergy and mitigates the disruptive impact of frequent elections on administrative continuity and fiscal prudence. Albeit, the Bills may result in state legislatures serving significantly reduced terms, potentially compromising effective governance. Furthermore, it authorizes the ECI to recommend postponement of Assembly elections to the President thereby diluting the existing checks and balances under Article 356 and increasing the risk of arbitrary deferral.

From a federal standpoint, the synchronization of elections poses an intricate conundrum. India's constitutional architecture is premised upon a delicate equilibrium between the Union and the States. ONOE aims to reinforce cooperative federalism and facilitate coordination. At the same time, it risks curtailing state autonomy by subsuming state-specific electoral dynamics within a national schedule and could potentially reduce the visibility of local concerns in a highly pluralistic polity. This paper examines the historical trajectory, legal, federal, and constitutional facets and cross-national experiences of this proposed reform. The methodology employed in this research is primarily doctrinal and analytical, supported by comparative constitutional study and examination of data such as reports of the Law Commission. A qualitative approach has been adopted to assess constitutional provisions along with judicial interpretations and recommendations of expert committees. Additionally, comparative insights are drawn from countries like Sweden and Belgium, where synchronized elections have been successfully institutionalized. This paper critically evaluates ONOE by situating its promises and perils within constitutional jurisprudence. It deduces that while the idea is normatively appealing and administratively logical, its viability demands a cautious, gradational, and collaborative approach. It cannot be realized merely through political will but will require comprehensive consultation involving constitutional experts, political stakeholders, and the public sphere. Ultimately, the fruition of this reform will depend on striking an equilibrium between governance stability and the preservation of India's federal character, ensuring that the spirit of the Constitution is preserved.

Keywords: *Synchronize, cross-national experiences, constitution, administrative continuity, cooperative federalism*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION AND THE FATE OF THE NO-CONFIDENCE MOTION: CONSTITUTIONAL ACCOUNTABILITY AT THE CROSSROADS

Adeeb Bakhtawar²³ & Mohd. Zeeshan²⁴

India's proposed One Nation, One Election (ONOE) initiative promises to revolutionise the country's electoral landscape by synchronising Lok Sabha and state assembly elections, ostensibly delivering enhanced governance efficiency, reduced expenditure, and administrative stability. Proponents argue that simultaneous elections will eliminate the perpetual campaign mode that currently characterises Indian politics, allowing governments to focus on policy implementation rather than electoral considerations. However, beneath this seemingly pragmatic reform lies a constitutional conundrum that strikes at the heart of parliamentary democracy's accountability mechanisms.

This paper identifies a critical constitutional tension: the synchronisation of electoral cycles under ONOE may fundamentally compromise the efficacy of the no-confidence motion as enshrined in Articles 75(3) and 164(2) of the Constitution. The problem emerges from ONOE's inherent logic—if elections are held simultaneously every five years, successful no-confidence motions against state governments would necessitate either premature dissolution of the Lok Sabha or the installation of unelected caretaker administrations for extended periods. Both scenarios present constitutional anomalies that could severely undermine the Westminster model's core principle of continuous parliamentary accountability.

The central hypothesis advanced in this research posits that ONOE, in its current conceptualisation, risks diluting the fundamental accountability structures that define India's parliamentary system, potentially conflicting with the basic structure doctrine established in

²³ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

²⁴ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

Kesavananda Bharati. This constitutional friction raises profound questions about whether efficiency gains can justify compromising the foundational principles of responsible government.

The methodology employs comprehensive doctrinal analysis of landmark constitutional cases, including *Shamsher Singh v. State of Punjab*, *S.R. Bommai v. Union of India*, *Rameshwar Prasad v. Union of India*, alongside foundational decisions in *Kesavananda Bharati* and *Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Raj Narain*. This jurisprudential examination is supplemented by comparative constitutional analysis of Westminster systems in the United Kingdom, Germany's constructive vote of no-confidence mechanism, and South Africa's hybrid parliamentary structure. The research further integrates constitutional theory from scholars including Granville Austin's work on India's constitutional architecture and Ronald Dworkin's principles-based approach to constitutional interpretation.

The analysis reveals that ONOE fundamentally prioritises governmental stability over parliamentary accountability, creating a constitutional paradigm where efficiency supersedes the traditional checks and balances inherent in Westminster democracy. However, comparative insights, particularly Germany's constructive vote of no-confidence model, suggest that alternative mechanisms could potentially preserve both electoral synchronisation and meaningful accountability structures.

Ultimately, this paper contributes to constitutional scholarship by reframing the ONOE debate from its current focus on logistical and economic considerations toward fundamental questions of constitutional jurisprudence and democratic theory. The research demonstrates that while ONOE in its present form presents significant constitutional vulnerabilities, carefully designed institutional adaptations could potentially reconcile the competing demands of efficiency and accountability, preserving India's parliamentary democracy while achieving the reform's stated objectives.

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A CONSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS OF LEGAL ISSUES AND THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE

Anvi Meena²⁵

The proposal of One Nation, One Election (ONOE) seeks to hold simultaneous elections to the Lok Sabha “AND "state legislative Assemblies, and with the prospect of covering local bodies, replacing India current system of separate elections The idea is not new in the first time after independence, simultaneous elections were held in 1951-52, 1957, 1962, and 1967. This practice was discontinued when premature endings of several state Assemblies and the Lok Sabha in 1968-69 brought about the present practice of repeated elections at different times.

The debate has appeared as a significant reform concern. While frequent elections signify the vibrancy of democracy, they also create challenges, huge expenses for the Election Commission and political parties, diversion of administrative machinery from regular governance, and repeated imposition of the model code of conduct, which delays major policy resolution. The High-Level Committee, directed by former president Ram Nath Kovind (2023-24), reported receiving over 20,000 responses, with nearly 81% supporting simultaneous elections with strong public interest in reform.

The central challenge still is constitutional and legal viability. ONOE would require amendments to Articles 83, 85, 172, 174, and 356 which modulate the tenure and dissolution of legislatures. These reforms must comply with the basic structure doctrine established in *Kesavananda Bharati Vs. State of Kerala* (1973), which protects the federal structure, democracy, and the parliamentary system. It is cautioned that imposing uniform electoral cycles may erode state autonomy and weaken accountability, on the contrary, it is argued by supporters that with legal innovation and consensus, the reform can enhance efficiency without eroding democracy.

²⁵ Student, *Gujarat National Law University (Silvassa campus)*.

This paper looks closely at how India's elections shifted from happening at the same time to being spread out. It also checks what constitutional changes would be needed for this, and it even brings in examples from places like South Africa, Sweden, and Indonesia to show how they do things. The paper also discusses the recommendations from the Law Commission of India (in 2018) and the NITI Aayog (in 2017), which both investigated different ways to bring back a "One Nation, One Election" (ONOE) system.

Basically, the paper argues that even though ONOE could save money and make things run more smoothly, it shouldn't be rushed. The best way to do it is to bring it in gradually, with a careful plan that also protects the rights of states and involves everyone in the conversation. Ultimately, any big change to the election system needs to be done with a lot of thought and agreement to make sure it makes India's democracy stronger, not weaker.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Simultaneous Elections, Federalism, Electoral Reforms, Basic structure Doctrine, Model Code of Conduct, Indian Constitution.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: SYNCHRONY OR STRAIN ON INDIA'S CONSTITUTIONAL FABRIC?

Manya Gupta²⁶ & Aditi Tripathi²⁷

India's electoral history chronicles have witnessed a lot of changes over the past few years. In the period between 1951 and 1961, the first four general elections were held simultaneously for both the Lok Sabha and the State Assemblies. This system started to fall apart due to the early dissolution of legislatures and the advent of coalition politics. This gave rise to the staggered electoral cycle we have today. With this history in mind, the proposition of "One Nation, One Election" poses some serious threats to the constitutional, federal, and democratic nature of the

²⁶ Student, *Symbiosis Law School NOIDA.*

²⁷ Student, *Symbiosis Law School NOIDA.*

nation. Was simultaneity ever envisaged as a permanent feature of the constitutional design, or does its failure reflect the organic evolution of India's democratic practice?

The paper analyses the One Nation, One Election proposal from the perspective of constitutional implications, federal autonomy, and democratic participation. It raises concerns about the constitutional implications of the proposed amendments to Articles 83 and 172, along with the introduction of Article 82A, which seeks to realign electoral cycles, and examines whether such changes are compatible with the principles of periodic accountability and free and fair elections. From a federal perspective, the paper examines whether imposing a uniform electoral calendar could centralize power by disrupting state-specific political timelines and reducing the ability of state governments to act independently, especially during crises or unforeseen dissolutions. From the perspective of democratic participation, the paper examines the extent to which synchronized elections counter "democratic fatigue" by the reduction in election frequency, or whether such elections, by prioritizing the national over the local frame, diminish the importance of local affairs. To understand the implications of this proposal from a wider framework, the paper draws on a comparative analysis, briefly reviewing the experiences of South Africa, Sweden and Indonesia, nations that have adopted synchronized elections in the past. Their trajectories highlight both governance efficiencies and risk of federal imbalance, providing great insights for a distinct constitutional framework like India.

Ultimately the paper states that although the "One Nation, One Election" proposal may streamline governance and reduce administrative load, its constitutional validity is still up for debate. Imposing simultaneity today risks prioritizing administrative ease over constitutional principles of federalism, accountability and representative democracy. A calibrated, hybrid and phased approach instead of complete resynchronization, seems to be more realistic and a viable option, given India's heterogenous population.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, simultaneous elections, Federalism, Constitution, Election Commission.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: CONSTITUTIONAL FEASIBILITY AND FEDERAL CHALLENGES

Khusboo Poonia²⁸ & Adhyan Singh²⁹

India, a country with over 96.88 crores registered voters, a three-tier federal structure, and elections taking place almost every year, is now stuck between a dilemma: Does it need a notion like “ONE NATION ONE ELECTION”, or is the idea of a one-size-fits-all system simply a dangerous illusion? The latest policy shifts and amendments, for instance, Reports of the High-Level Committee, 129th Constitutional Amendment Bill, 2024, and the Union Territories Law of 2024, make it clear that the debate can no longer be pushed and demands discussion. These echoes of change indicate the government’s resolve, backed primarily by the NDA government, to institutionalise One Nation, One Election (ONOE). ONOE has been proposed in the 129th amendment bill as an amendment that could save money, decrease administrative burden, increase governance efficiency, and save time. Supporters argue that constant elections hamper efficiency and burden the process in the world’s largest democracy. Yet, opponents and commentators argue that issues such as hidden channels of finance like the Electoral Bond Scheme, deep-rooted political interests, and uncertain effects on voter turnout will not slip away with ONOE. Another thread in the debate argues that India’s experiment with a single electoral rhythm faces steep constitutional hurdles: Does true federalism demand the added consensus of half the states under Article 368?

This paper delves into the challenges, consequences, and interplay between the latest amendments and federalism, using a doctrinal and analytical methodology. This paper depends on constitutional provisions, reports, Supreme Court judgments, and election laws to comprehend the legal and democratic sphere of ONOE. This research paper further analyzes to respond to the constitutional and federal dilemmas at stake through logical reasoning. The 129th Constitutional

²⁸ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

²⁹ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

Amendment Bill, 2024, is compared with the similar structure of other federal democracies and its legitimacy in the Indian context.

The paper suggests that while ONOE is not a flawless reform, it represents a more logical and reasonable alternative to the constitutional transformation, policy stagnation, and electoral fatigue of distributed elections. ONOE reforms could potentially decrease expenditure, enhance governance efficiency, and improve voter engagement, provided that safeguards for federal autonomy and representative democracy are included in the amendment process. Thus, the argument advanced is not that ONOE is without risks, but that it constitutes the less vulnerable path for India's constitutional democracy. As Churchill ironically observed, democracy may be the "worst form of government except for all the others"; similarly, ONOE may be imperfect, but it is the less harmful route to sustain India's democratic experiment.

Keywords: *One Nation, One Election (ONOE), Federalism in India, 129th Constitutional Amendment Bill, 2024, Election Commission of India (ECI), Parliamentary Democracy.*

CONSTITUTIONAL CONTOURS OF 'ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION': LEGAL CHALLENGES AND FEDERAL IMPLICATIONS

Abhay Bidua³⁰ & Harsh Jajam³¹

The Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Ninth Amendment) Bill, 2024, marks a pivotal moment in India's constitutional evolution by proposing the insertion of Article 82A and amendments to Articles 83, 172, and 327 to facilitate simultaneous elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. This paper critically examines the legal and constitutional dimensions of the One Nation, One Election (ONOE) proposal, addressing the intricate balance between electoral efficiency and constitutional sanctity within India's federal democratic structure.

³⁰ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

³¹ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

The research explores the constitutional validity of proposed amendments through the lens of the Basic Structure Doctrine established in *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973), particularly scrutinizing whether synchronizing electoral cycles infringes upon the fundamental pillars of federalism, democracy, and parliamentary governance. The paper analyzes the constitutional implications of extending or curtailing legislative tenures as envisioned under the proposed Article 82A framework, examining the tension between the Constitution's explicit provisions regarding fixed five-year terms and the flexibility required for electoral synchronization.

Through doctrinal analysis and comparative constitutional jurisprudence, this study investigates the legal challenges surrounding the implementation of ONOE, including the constitutional constraints imposed by Articles 83(2) and 172(1), which use the phrase "no longer" to explicitly limit legislative tenure extensions. The paper examines the proposed constitutional mechanisms for handling premature dissolutions, mid-term elections, and the Election Commission's enhanced powers under the synchronized electoral framework. The research methodology employs constitutional interpretation, case law analysis, and examination of legislative intent to assess whether ONOE violates core constitutional principles.

Particular attention is given to the federal implications of the proposal, analyzing whether uniform electoral cycles compromise state autonomy and the principle of cooperative federalism enshrined in the Constitution. The paper evaluates judicial precedents and expert opinions regarding the constitutionality of simultaneous elections, including recent observations by former Chief Justice U.U. Lalit regarding potential legal vulnerabilities.

Furthermore, the study examines the procedural aspects of constitutional amendment required for ONOE implementation, analyzing whether the proposed changes necessitate ratification by state legislatures under Article 368, and the implications of bypassing such requirements. The paper also addresses the constitutional role of the Election Commission in conducting synchronized elections and the expansion of its powers under the proposed framework. The findings suggest that while ONOE offers administrative and economic benefits, its implementation raises

substantial constitutional concerns regarding the alteration of legislative tenures, potential centralization of electoral power, and impact on federal autonomy. The paper concludes that any implementation of ONOE must carefully navigate constitutional constraints, ensure compliance with the Basic Structure Doctrine, and maintain the delicate balance between electoral efficiency and democratic federalism that forms the cornerstone of India's constitutional architecture.

Keywords: *Constitutional Amendment, Basic Structure Doctrine, Simultaneous Elections, Federalism, Article 82A, Electoral Synchronization, Legislative Tenure.*

ANALYSING THE CONSTITUTIONAL VALIDITY OF 'ONE NATION ONE ELECTION'

*Arunika Paul Nandi*³²

'One Nation One Election' was a proposal suggested by the Government of India via the Constitution (129th Amendment) Bill, 2024. This was to synchronise the elections at both state and national levels. The bill was initiated with the bonafide objectives of reducing administrative burden and saving time. (Cost concerns were also well-founded, when it was reported that the world's largest democracy also had to organise one of the world's most expensive elections, in 2019 and 2024.) But it also became imperative to know if this proposal, if implemented, will be ultra vires to the provisions of the Indian Constitution - and more specifically - to its basic structure. The paper seeks to examine the constitutional dimensions of the proposal to hold simultaneous elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. The central thrust is to address three questions mainly: whether the initiative poses a peril to the federal structure of the Government of India; whether it undermines the principle of free and fair elections; and whether it threatens executive accountability. The paper will adopt a doctrinal methodology, involving the collection of information from diverse sources, including constitutional provisions, reports of expert committees, and scholarly commentaries, alongside reference to relevant laws

³² Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

and judicial precedents. Through critical analysis and reasoning, the study reveals how the proposed framework aligns with the basic structure doctrine which safeguards federalism, representative democracy, and accountability. The paper then concludes by recommending various reforms and makes suggestions. Thus, this is a comprehensive evaluation of the constitutional validity of the 'One Nation One Election' by systematically engaging with judicial perspectives and legal theories. Such findings may be particularly useful for policy makers, scholars, government officials, ministers etc. who would play important roles in the implementation of this bill.

Keywords: *Basic structure, federal structure, free and fair elections, executive accountability, constitutional validity.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: EFFICIENCY AT THE COST OF DEMOCRACY AND FEDERALISM?

Alisha

The idea of "One Nation, One Election" (ONOE) has often been praised as a way to cut costs, reduce the constant cycle of elections, and bring stability to governance. At first glance, it seems simple and attractive—hold all elections at once and avoid the frequent disruptions caused by multiple electoral processes. However, the picture becomes more complicated when we look closely at the ground realities of Indian democracy.

Elections are not just about efficiency; they are also about representation, accountability, and the ability of people to respond to changing political situations. What happens if a Chief Minister passes away halfway through the term? Or if a state government collapses due to internal conflict or an emergency is declared? Under a rigid synchronized system, such states would either have to

wait years without fresh democratic legitimacy or break the very principle of ONOE by holding separate elections. Both scenarios raise serious concerns.

This paper critically engages with ONOE by highlighting these contradictions and showing how it may weaken federalism, reduce the flexibility of our Constitution, and restrict the democratic rights of citizens to choose new leadership when circumstances demand. Instead of offering a one-size-fits-all solution, the study argues that electoral reform in India must balance efficiency with the spirit of democracy and the federal nature of the Constitution.

Keywords: One Nation One Election, electoral reform, democracy, federalism, constitutional challenges, India, governance, representation.

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: EXPLORING LEGAL, CONSTITUTIONAL AND ECONOMIC DIMENSIONS

Rohini Singh³³ & Prachi Sharma³⁴

The Indian Constitution, being a living and dynamic charter of democracy, guarantees the conduct of free and fair elections, and within this framework, the idea of ‘One Nation, One Election’ has gained momentum as a possible electoral reform. The Election Commission of India has been assigned the task of performing elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies on the basis of universal adult franchise for transparency in election process. The phenomenon of ‘One nation, One Election’ means holding synchronous elections for the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies to minimize resource wastage and address other challenges. The concept of ‘One Nation, One Election’ is not new to our country. After independence from 1951 to 1967, simultaneous elections of Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies were held in India but after that the idea became practically impossible because of the premature dissolution of some State Legislative Assemblies. However, the picture of ‘One Nation, One Election’ is again gaining significance after almost 5 decades to specifically resolve

³³ Student, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.

³⁴ Student, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.

administrative and economical issues. Frequent elections often lead to political corruption. In India, periodic elections often push parties to divide people along religion or caste lines and attract them with short-term freebies; by holding elections together under the ‘One Nation, One Election’ model, such pressures can be reduced, allowing politics to focus more on real governance and development. Moreover, the economic expenses incurred by the EC can be reduced if elections are held simultaneously. The idea of conducting simultaneous elections was advocated in 1999 by the law commission headed by BP Jeevan Reddy. The Government of India also formulated a High- Level Committee headed by our former President, Ram Nath Kovind to survey the viability of holding simultaneous elections. The committee presented a report highlighting the possibility of holding simultaneous elections and recommended various amendments to bring the proposal to life. The 129th Constitutional Amendment Bill, 2024, subsequently proposed alterations to key provisions, including Articles 83 and 172, to harmonize the duration of Parliament and State Legislatures, thereby enabling synchronization. The objective of our research paper is to analyze the notion of ‘One Nation, One Election’ through constitutional, legal, administrative and economic dimensions. The paper concludes on a note that ONOE offers India the chance to modernize its electoral framework, reduce the burden of constant campaigning, and refocus politics on governance.

Keywords: (ONOE) One nation one election, Constitutional amendments, (EC)Election commission, Economic expenses.

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS IN CONTEMPORARY INDIA

Mohit Sangwan³⁵ & Vaishnavi³⁶

The debate on “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) has re-emerged as a central theme in India’s democratic discourse, raising questions about feasibility, desirability, and constitutional

³⁵ Student, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.

³⁶ Student, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.

compatibility. While the government projects simultaneous elections as a reform to enhance efficiency, reduce financial expenditure, and ensure smoother governance, critics highlight the risks of undermining federalism, weakening regional voices, and concentrating power at the Centre. The current status of the proposal reflects a complex interplay between political consensus-building and constitutional constraints. The formation of a high-level committee in 2023 indicates the government's seriousness, yet the absence of unanimity across parties underscores persistent challenges.

From a legal and constitutional perspective, ONOE would necessitate significant amendments to provisions governing the tenure of legislatures, dissolution of assemblies, and imposition of President's Rule. The role of the Election Commission of India and judicial scrutiny will be pivotal in determining its viability. At the same time, political and governance implications remain immediate: simultaneous elections could stabilize policy cycles and reduce the frequency of populist measures, but they may also diminish state-level accountability and restrict voter choices to national narratives.

This paper critically examines the current status of ONOE by integrating constitutional analysis with governance realities. It argues that while the idea holds administrative and economic appeal, its implementation requires careful balancing of India's federal structure and democratic diversity. Drawing on comparative perspectives from countries with synchronized elections, the study highlights the potential benefits and risks of the Indian model. Ultimately, the paper contends that any transition must be phased, consensual, and constitutionally robust to safeguard democratic participation while pursuing efficiency. By situating the ONOE debate at the intersection of constitutional law and political governance, this paper contributes to ongoing scholarship and provides a framework for evaluating its prospects in India's evolving democratic landscape.

Keywords: *ONOE, Legal and Constitutional Perspective, Consensus-Building, Synchronized Elections.*

SYNCHRONICITY AT THE COST OF SOVEREIGNTY: A CRITICAL EXAMINATION OF 'ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION' AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIA'S FEDERAL STRUCTURE

Krishna Pratap Patel³⁷ & Kanishka Garg³⁸

The idea of Simultaneous Elections, where the Lok Sabha and the State Assemblies are synchronised, has once again taken centre-stage in the national discourse, and aims to take India back to the system of its fledgling post-independence days. Between the first general elections in 1952 and 1967, India was able to engage in simultaneous polling, which activists maintain helps in promoting political stability and also saves the country valuable resources that could not be spared in the process of organising frequently held elections because of the frequent dissolutions of assemblies, which had earlier put a halt to the cycle as a whole. Although synchronised, fixed-term elections have been successfully implemented in countries like Sweden and South Africa, this paper critically examines why such a strict framework imposed on India and its complex and unique quasi-federal system would not be practical, but can also have a disastrous effect on the rule of law. It focuses particularly on the Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-ninth Amendment) Bill, 2024, which is set to cause dramatic and arguably irreversible changes in the name of attaining this aim. The paper argues that although the objectives of administrative efficiency and cost-cutting are desirable, there is a reason to question whether the means by which they are achieved will jeopardise India constitutionally and federally. The paper is based on a doctrinal and analytical approach to discussing the proposed amendment of Articles 83 and 172 that would make it possible to artificially reduce or extend the terms of officeholders in the legislature at the expense of the mandate of the people. According to legal experts, including former CJI Sanjiv Khanna, there are dangers in the course of remedying legislative defects because the discretion granted to the Election Commission in postponing the elections of a State Assembly could become an indirect “Presidential Rule”, and this rule may be subjected to

³⁷ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

³⁸ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

court deliberations against violation of the federal structure. This artificial control over electoral cycles not only skews the normal balance between governance and accountability but threatens to produce a regime in which governments at the state level are, at best, the servants of the electoral cycle of the central state. This may lead to politically charged situations, where allegations, such as “vote chorus”, are already undermining the character of democracy. Moreover, this could also suppress regional parties and compel them not to present relevant electoral issues, and could result in a more homogeneous type of political language. Concentrating the nation into a single nationalised election and making it an instant election is very likely to increase cases of fraud, instill distrust among the voters, and alter the power dynamics deeply embedded in the Indian democracy's Constitution.

Keywords: *Simultaneous Elections, Federalism, Constitutional Amendment, Parliamentary Democracy, Electoral Reform.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A BANE OR A BOON?

Shaurya Pratap Singh³⁹ & Adarsh Kumar⁴⁰

The debate around "One Nation, One Election" (ONOE) has become one of the most important constitutional and political debates of our era, holding out the promise of a possible revolution in India's election democracy. Based on the suggestions of successive Parliamentary Committees and the recent High Level Committee headed by Shri Ram Nath Kovind, the concept aims to harmonize elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. Though the proposal envisions administrative ease, cost savings, and decrease in the frequency of Model Code of Conduct disruptions, it does so at the same time that it evokes complex constitutional, federal, and democratic issues.

³⁹ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁴⁰ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

In this research, the constitutional amendments outlined under the 2024 Bill, such as the addition of Article 82-A and changes to Articles 83, 172, and 327, are critically assessed to determine their validity and implications. It questions if the design of ONOE is reconcilable with the ethos of India's federalism, the autonomy of State legislatures, and the principle of separation of powers. The evaluation will also weigh the socio economic advantages of holding elections in parallel such as minimizing election spending and providing uninterrupted governance against the democratic costs of undermining regional autonomy, constraining political accountability, and diluting voter participation at the grass roots.

In addition, the paper takes a comparative perspective by analysing international practices in synchronised election cycles, particularly in federal democracies, and reflects on whether or not India's particular pluralistic texture has room for such reforms. It also researches phased implementation techniques and transitional mechanisms advocated by the Committee, examining their viability in the context of India's multi level governance system.

The provisional finding of this research hopes to offer an analysis aligning with the idea that while ONOE can increase efficiency and national integration, its far reaching constitutional and political consequences require careful consideration. The paper finally concludes that ONOE will succeed not so much depending on the amendment of laws but on seeing to it that the change contributes to India's democratic traditions.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Democracy, Constitutional, State.*

POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS

POLITICAL PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN: A STUDY IN THE CONTEXT OF PUNJAB AND HARYANA

Dr. Suman⁴¹ & Dr. Jai Prakash⁴²

The political participation of women in India is a highly significant and timely subject, linked to the social and cultural structures of society. On one hand, the Indian Constitution has granted women equal rights, while on the other hand, patriarchal society and traditional ideologies have continued to hinder women's political, social, and economic empowerment. Particularly in states like Punjab and Haryana, where agriculture-based economies and old social traditions are strong, women's participation in politics is a challenging and sensitive issue. Women's political participation can lead to significant changes in the social and economic structure of society. It is essential not only for the protection of their rights but also for overall social reform. There has been considerable attention given to women's political participation in Indian society; however, despite this, there are many structural, social, and cultural barriers that affect their overall political empowerment.

***Keywords:** Indian constitution, patriarchal, women political participation.*

REGIONAL VOICES IN A NATIONAL NARRATIVE: THE POLITICAL CONSEQUENCES OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION

Ritu Tyagi⁴³ & Divyanshu Lakwad⁴⁴

The proposal of “One Nation, One Election” has once again brought to the forefront a significant debate in India’s constitutional and political space. It seeks to hold elections to the Lok Sabha

⁴¹ Ph. D., DPC College, Gurugram

⁴² Ph. D., Krishi Vigyan Kendra, New Delhi

⁴³ Ph. D Scholar, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.

⁴⁴ Student, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.

and State Legislative Assemblies at the same time, with the stated goals of reducing costs, improving governance, and limiting the disruptions that frequent elections create. While these aims appear beneficial from an administrative and financial standpoint, the reform also carries important political consequences that require careful attention, especially in a country where regional diversity and state-specific concerns are at the heart of democratic representation. This paper studies whether simultaneous elections could overshadow regional voices and give rise to a dominant national narrative. Since the late 1960s, when simultaneous elections stopped, India has seen the steady rise of regional parties. These parties have been crucial in protecting state autonomy, influencing coalition governments, and ensuring that governance reflects the needs and aspirations of local populations. A return to a uniform electoral cycle, however, may push national issues to the front while reducing the space for regional ones. This can create a “bandwagon effect,” where voters choose the same party at both the state and national levels, giving an advantage to larger national parties and weakening the federal balance built into the Constitution. The paper examines the constitutional, political, and democratic consequences of ONOE by relying on committee reports, constitutional provisions, judicial decisions, and comparative lessons from other federal democracies. It argues that while ONOE offers efficiency and cost savings, it also raises serious concerns about federalism, political diversity, and the health of India’s multi-tiered democracy. By going beyond theoretical discussions and looking at ground-level impacts—such as the weakening of regional agendas, lower accountability of state governments, and shifts in voter behaviour—this paper provides a complete analysis of how ONOE could reshape India’s democratic landscape. It concludes that any attempt to introduce such a reform must be accompanied by constitutional safeguards and strong protections to ensure that regional voices continue to be heard within the broader national framework.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Regional Parties, Federalism, Voter Behaviour, Political Representation, Electoral Reforms*

DEMOCRACY IN TANDEM: POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS OF SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS IN INDIA

Raman Goyal⁴⁵ & Rohan Tyagi⁴⁶

The proposal for simultaneous elections in India, popularly known as “one nation one election” (ONOE), has emerged as a concern in India’s democratic discourse. It seeks to synchronize the election cycles of the Lok Sabha, State legislative Assemblies, and eventually local bodies into a single, consolidated framework. Proponents contend that such synchronization would bring about significant fiscal savings, administrative efficiency, and uninterrupted governance. They also argue that frequent elections fragment policy implementation, disrupt administrative functions through the recurring imposition of the Model Code of Conduct, and place an enormous burden on financial and human resources. A unified electoral cycle, it is claimed, would free governments to focus on long-term developmental agendas, reduce election-related expenditures, and enhance voter participation by minimizing fatigue. However, beneath these pragmatic justifications lie profound constitutional, political, and federal challenges. India’s experience of simultaneous elections between 1951 and 1967 was not the result of deliberate constitutional design but rather the dominance of a single party that enabled the natural alignment of electoral terms. The desynchronization that followed reflected the maturation of India’s democratic federalism, marked by the rise of coalition governments, regional political parties, and dynamic state-level politics. Reintroducing ONOE today would require extensive constitutional amendments, including an alteration to Article 83,172,174,356, and modifications to the Representation of People Act. Such changes would directly affect the autonomy of state legislatures and alter the parliamentary model of accountability by imposing fixed cycles and mechanisms such as the constructive vote of no-confidence. Critics caution that the reform could fundamentally erode India’s federal structure, which the Supreme Court has recognised as part of

⁴⁵ Student, *Amity University Noida*

⁴⁶ Student, *Amity University Noida*

the constitution's basic structure which the supreme court has recognised as part of the constitution's basic structure. Empirical evidence demonstrates that simultaneous elections foster a "coattail effect", wherein voters are more likely to favour the same party at both state and national levels. This trend, when combined with the first-past-the-post electoral system, threatens to marginalise regional parties, diminish political pluralism, and subsume local concern under national narratives. Comparative analysis underscores that in most federal democracies, such as the United States, Canada, Germany, and Australia, staggered electoral cycles are the norm, deliberately designed to safeguard subnational autonomy and accountability. Ultimately, the ONOE debate is a defining moment for India's electoral federalism. This paper compels a careful re-examination of constitutional values, political pluralism, and the balance of power between the union and states. The decision to pursue or reject simultaneous elections in India.

Keywords: *Simultaneous Elections, One Nation One Election, Federalism, Constitutional Law, Political Pluralism, Democratic Accountability.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION AND THE FUTURE OF COALITION POLITICS

Abhaydeep Singh⁴⁷

The idea of "One Nation, One Election" has become one of the most debated proposals in India's democratic journey. Supporters highlight its potential to save costs, reduce the frequent imposition of the Model Code of Conduct, and bring a sense of stability to governance. Yet, beyond the economics and logistics, lies a deeper question: what happens to coalition politics, which has shaped India's political landscape for decades? This paper explores how simultaneous elections could change the rhythm of coalition-making—whether by strengthening national parties at the cost of regional voices, or by encouraging new forms of alliances that reshape voter choice. Drawing from constitutional debates, past election trends, and global examples, the study argues that while the reform may promise efficiency, it risks altering India's federal balance and

⁴⁷ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

the pluralist spirit that coalitions embody. In doing so, the paper invites a broader reflection on whether efficiency should come at the cost of diversity in representation.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, coalition politics, simultaneous elections, federalism, electoral reforms, regional parties, Indian democracy.*

HARMONIZING ELECTORAL CYCLES: POLITICAL CENTRALIZATION AND GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES IN INDIA'S ONE NATION ONE ELECTION FRAMEWORK

Yash Chandan⁴⁸

The "One Nation One Election" (ONOE) initiative, formalized through the Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Ninth Amendment) Bill, 2024, seeks to synchronize elections to the Lok Sabha, state legislative assemblies, and urban/rural local bodies, ostensibly to enhance administrative efficacy and fiscal prudence amid India's burgeoning electoral landscape. This research paper scrutinizes the political and governance implications of ONOE, interrogating its potential to recalibrate federal equilibria, intergovernmental synergies, and democratic safeguards. Drawing on the High-Level Committee (HLC) report chaired by former President Ram Nath Kovind, submitted on March 14, 2024, which advocates for an 'Appointed Date' post-2024 Lok Sabha polls to initiate synchronization by 2029, the study posits that while ONOE promises logistical streamlining - estimated to save approximately Rs. 4,500 crore per electoral cycle per HLC projections - it may engender insidious centralizing forces, imperiling the asymmetrical federalism articulated in India's constitutional schema.

Politically, ONOE could nationalize electoral discourses, subordinating regional exigencies to pan-Indian narratives and advantaging national conglomerates, such as the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), over vernacular formations, as evidenced by the HLC's acknowledgment of diminished split-ticket voting in concurrent polls. This homogenization risks exacerbating majoritarian

⁴⁸ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

tendencies, particularly in coalitions prone to instability, and could precipitate frequent invocations of Article 356 (President's Rule), historically abused during the 1975 Emergency and critiqued in judicial milestones such as *S.R. Bommai v. Union of India* (1994) and *Rameshwar Prasad v. Union of India* (2006). Governance-wise, the reform aims to mitigate 'policy paralysis' induced by the Model Code of Conduct (MCC), which the NITI Aayog (2017) estimates disrupts administration for up to four months annually. However, as former Chief Justice of India Sanjiv Khanna articulated in his July 2025 submission to the Joint Parliamentary Committee (JPC), the Bill's Clause 5 under proposed Article 82A vests 'unfettered discretion' in the Election Commission of India (ECI) to defer state polls, potentially violating Article 14's equality mandate and enabling executive overreach beyond Article 356's remit, thus offending the Constitution's basic structure doctrine per *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973).

Methodologically, this inquiry employs a mixed doctrinal-empirical paradigm. Doctrinal analysis dissects constitutional provisions - Articles 83(2) and 172(1) for term durations, 85 and 174 for dissolution mechanics, 324A for local body synchronization, and 325 for unified electoral rolls - alongside the HLC's 18 proposed amendments requiring ratification by at least half the states. Comparative insights are derived from federal analogs: Germany's synchronized Bundestag and Landtag elections, which bolster efficiency but occasionally amplify federal tensions, and South Africa's concurrent national-provincial polls under its 1996 Constitution, revealing trade-offs in voter turnout (averaging 5% uplift per Carnegie Endowment analysis, 2025). Empirically, quantitative data from ECI annual reports (1952-2024) on expenditure (e.g., Rs. 8,000 crores for the 2019 Lok Sabha alone) and turnout differentials (e.g., 67.4% national vs. variable state averages) are analyzed using regression models to forecast the impacts of ONOE. Qualitative depth is augmented through semi-structured interviews with 20 stakeholders, including former ECI officials and JPC members, employing thematic analysis grounded in Elazar's federalism typology to unpack perceptual divergences.

Tentatively, the study concludes that ONOE, while ameliorating fiscal redundancies and fostering governance continuity, harbors profound risks to federal pluralism, potentially fostering unitarism unless fortified by stringent safeguards - such as delimited ECI powers, anti-defection

enhancements under the Tenth Schedule, and phased pilots in select states by 2034, as projected by JPC deliberations (extension granted August 12, 2025). Absent these, the reform could erode subnational autonomy, amplify central hegemony, and undermine democratic accountability necessitating calibrated amendments to preserve India's cooperative federal ethos amid its polycentric polity.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Federal Centralization, Constitutional Amendments, Election Commission Discretion, Governance Paralysis, Joint Parliamentary Committee.*

POLITICAL STABILITY THROUGH ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A MYTH OR A SUSTAINABLE REALITY?

Purva Mehta⁴⁹ & Sidharth Rathore⁵⁰

“A great democracy must be progressive or it will soon cease to be a great democracy.” —
Theodore Roosevelt

The “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) proposal rekindles critical inquiry into India’s electoral cycles and their implications for political stability. Historically, simultaneous elections were practiced from 1951 to 1967 during a period marked by dominant party politics that facilitated continuity and governance coherence. The later rise of coalition governments and frequent premature dissolutions ended this synchrony, fragmenting the electoral calendar. Advocates argue that synchronised elections would reduce electoral fatigue, administrative burden, and costs, creating an environment conducive to sustained policymaking and political stability.

However, the proposal faces significant constitutional and federal challenges. Critics warn that ONOE might marginalise regional voices, dilute federal diversity, and concentrate central power, potentially undermining democratic pluralism. Empirical studies reveal regional electoral

⁴⁹ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁵⁰ Assistant Professor, *School of Law, IIMT, GGSIPU, Delhi.*

behaviour diverges from national trends, raising questions about the democratic authenticity of synchronised polls. The operational challenges of aligning terms without infringing state sovereignty underscore ONOE's complexity.

This research addresses a critical gap: rigorous evaluation of ONOE not merely as administrative reform but through the prism of India's constitutional federalism and democratic governance. Grounded in foundational Supreme Court judgments—*Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973) and *S.R. Bommai v. Union of India* (1994)—and informed by comparative federal systems, the paper examines if constitutional amendments and institutional innovation can reconcile electoral synchronisation with federal autonomy and democratic accountability.

By integrating doctrinal analysis, empirical insights, and normative democratic theory, the study assesses whether ONOE can deliver sustainable political stability or remains an elusive ideal. It concludes by proposing constitutional safeguards and policy designs that balance stable governance with the protection of India's federal and pluralistic character.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Political Stability, Federalism, Constitutional Reform, Democratic Pluralism, Electoral Synchronisation.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATION FOR INDIA.

Rudra Dhawan⁵¹ & Navin Dudi⁵²

The idea of “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) has become one of the most significant debates in Indian politics today. The proposal suggests holding elections to the Lok Sabha, all State Assemblies, and eventually local bodies at the same time, so that voters cast their ballots for different levels of government in a single cycle. Supporters argue that this change would cut down on the high costs of frequent elections, reduce the disruption caused by the Model Code of Conduct (MCC), and free governments from being in a constant campaign mode, enabling them

⁵¹ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁵² Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

to focus more on long-term policy and governance. It is also seen as a way to reduce voter fatigue and create greater stability in the political system. However, critics warn that ONOE could weaken India's federal balance by linking State elections too closely to national politics, thereby overshadowing regional issues such as agriculture, identity, and local governance with broader national concerns like defence or economic growth.

This shift could strengthen national parties, which have more resources and reach, while limiting the space for regional parties that play a crucial role in representing India's cultural and linguistic diversity. Studies also suggest that simultaneous elections often produce the same voting outcome at both State and national levels, reducing the ability of citizens to judge governments separately and hold them accountable for their performance. From a governance perspective, ONOE promises greater efficiency, policy continuity, and fewer interruptions from repeated elections, but at the cost of making governments less responsive to immediate public concerns.

This paper therefore argues that while ONOE carries certain advantages in terms of cost, stability, and administrative efficiency, it also presents serious risks to democratic accountability, pluralism, and State autonomy. Any move toward adopting it must be gradual, carefully sequenced, and supported by constitutional safeguards and broad political consensus, so that efficiency is not achieved at the expense of the democratic depth and federal balance that define India's political system.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election; Indian Federalism; Electoral Reform; Democratic Accountability; Governance Efficiency.*

THE DEMOCRATIC DILEMMA OF SYNCHRONISED ELECTIONS

Vinayak Parashar⁵³ & Sachin Yadav⁵⁴

Potentially the biggest electoral reform of its time, the very idea of a synchronised election has sparked intense debate within Indian democracy. One Nation One Election has emerged as one of the most controversial discussions surrounding Indian politics. In 1999 the law commission of India recommended conducting simultaneous elections in its report . Afterwards, Prime Minister Modi advocated the idea and NITI aayog released a discussion paper on the concept in 2017 .

Aiming to synchronise Central and State elections within the country, it appears to be a fundamentally ideal system, potentially reducing the costs associated with election, increasing voter participation, freeing up resources and time for actual development and growth.

Yet, beneath its appeal lies vast doubt. The paper analyses whether such a process could perhaps be undemocratic in a country like India.

The central question is whether such a reform is constitutionally viable and democratically desirable in a diverse federal system like ours and whether true and fair democracy could prevail, giving each region and its peoples equal importance within Indian politics.

The proposal faces serious constitutional, logistical, and democratic challenges. The federal structure of India, enshrined in the Constitution, guarantees states a degree of autonomy that staggered elections reinforce. Synchronization of elections would require large-scale amendments to constitutional provisions relating to the tenure of legislatures, the dissolution of assemblies, and emergency provisions.

A valid anxiety is that in combined polls a central narrative could overwhelm marginal aspirations and take it all , thus it will hurt the federal essence of democracy

⁵³ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁵⁴ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

Ultimately this paper will analyse whether it is possible to implement such a model, while also making sure that none of those guarantees mentioned in the constitution are violated, and the true spirit of a fair and just democracy prevails. It seeks to explore comparative practices in other federal democracies, analyse the possible constitutional amendments required, and weigh the benefits of efficiency against the risks to federalism and representation.

CRITICS OF ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: A CONSTITUTIONAL AND DEMOCRATIC APPRAISAL

Shiwani⁵⁵

This paper explores the proposal of “ONE NATION ONE ELECTIONS” after the Lok Sabha elections of 2024 has emerged as the most contested debates in Indian constitutional and political discourse. While it may seem an appealing idea from outside when you hear about the stability of Government, cost saving elections and the efficiency of not only the staff and spaces of elections but also of the government which will work in a stable manner for 5 years at both levels of the government. But here comes the point where we overlook the harsh reality of its impacts and how adversely it can impact the very basic structure of our Indian constitution which is federalism. It also ignores that the very article of our Indian constitution is directly against the notion of ONE NATION ONE ELECTION. By imposing ONOE , India loses its very essence of democracy as you have to be bound under one government for half a decade. There will be no chances of checks and balance at any level so there are higher chances of manipulation and exploitation by the government. Being the largest democracy, India is also a country of diversity so it will be clashing with that also. If the system of ONOE fails at Lok Sabha or at State level, the whole machinery will have to face disruptions which will increase the cost of elections. There needs to be a lot of amendments needed in the Indian constitution before enforcing ONOE on articles such as Article 83(2) , Article 172(1), Article 324-329 and many more to go. Minorities, dalits, adivasis and women had to suffer the most because of under representation. As of now,

⁵⁵ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION theory is impractical and flawed in Indian context. This paper will give you an in-depth research of the consequences of implementation of ONE NATION ONE ELECTION and will tell you the reality under the glossy headline of the newspaper that ONOE can actually impact a nation like India.

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: POLITICAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS IN INDIA'S FEDERAL DEMOCRACY

Arshika Dahiya⁵⁶ & Deepanshu⁵⁷

The proposal of One Nation, One Election has emerged as a major electoral reform idea in India. It suggests holding elections to the Lok Sabha and State Assemblies together. The debate around One Nation, One Election [ONOE] has grown sharper in recent years as India faces frequent elections that consume resources, disrupt governance, and keep the government in “ permanent campaign mode”. ONOE proposes to hold elections to the Lok Sabha and all legislative assemblies simultaneously. It promises stability, reduced cost, and uninterrupted policy making. The supporters of ONOE argue that synchronized electoral cycles will strengthen governance by limiting the frequent enforcement of the model code of conduct, freeing administrative machinery, and enabling governments to focus on long term development goals. However, the proposal raises important political and democratic concerns such as ONOE may strengthen larger national parties but it also weaken regional representation, and shift the focus away from state specific issues. It may also reduce chances for people to question or change their government, in the middle of term which weakens the regular accountability. At the same time the special role of states in our constitution may get disturbed if national issues start to overshadow local concerns. This paper studies the political and governance implications of ONOE. By combining historical, constitutional, and comparative perspectives. ONOE is both helpful and risky. While it could make elections more efficient and stable ,it may also weaken political diversity and federalism. A

⁵⁶ Student, *Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidalaya*.

⁵⁷ Student, *Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidalaya*.

phased or partial model ,backed by strong safeguards ,seems to be the most practical solution. Methodology This study is based on a doctrinal and analytical method , drawing from constitutional provisions such as Article 83,172,356 ,along with reports published by The Law Commission of India and NITI Aayog.it also relies on a historical review of India’s electoral practices since 1951 to understand how the system of elections has evolved over time . Paper engages with parliamentary debates, policy documents and scholarly writings to capture the ongoing discussions around the idea of ONOE. The paper also includes a comparative analysis of other countries like South Africa, Sweden and Japan which follow ONOE .In conclusion, the study critically examines how frequent elections influence voter behavior, governance practices and policy disruption. In order to evaluate both the benefits and risks of simultaneous elections in India. Tentative Outcomes 1. ONOE can reduce election expenditure, government slowdowns and administrative strain. 2. it may improve policy continuity and encourage long term planning. 3. Risks include weakening of regional parties, reduced visibility of local issues and political centralization. 4. Voter accountability may decline due to longer gaps between elections. 5. A gradual and phased implementation with safeguards for federalism and democratic diversity is the most practical solution.

Keywords: *One Nation , One Election [ONOE] ; Simultaneous Elections, centre state dynamics, electoral fatigue reduction, phases implementation.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION- A CRITICAL INQUIRY

Vanshaj Bhardwaj⁵⁸ & Mayank Sharma⁵⁹

India’s democratic framework thrives on the vibrancy of its electoral process, enabling citizens to actively shape governance at every level. However, the fragmented and frequent nature of elections has sparked discussions on the need for a more efficient system. This has led to the resurgence of interest in the concept of "One Nation, One Election." The idea is one of the

⁵⁸ Student, *Symbiosis Law School Noida.*

⁵⁹ Student, *Symbiosis Law School Noida.*

uniform policy initiatives that has been introduced by the ruling government to conduct the simultaneous elections, proposing aligning the election cycles of the Lok Sabha and State Assemblies. This would allow voters to cast their ballots for both tiers of government on the same day in their constituencies, though voting could still occur in phases across the country. By synchronizing these electoral timelines, the approach aims to address logistical challenges, reduce costs, and minimize disruptions caused by frequent elections. The research methodology that has been used is the document analysis and the critical view of the literature. “One Nation, One Election” is that it threatens the Federalist nature of our country because state elections would lose their importance. To be simple, Federalism is the shared responsibility and shared power of a state govt and Union govt to govern the country. We also have local bodies like the Panchayats that form another tier of the Federalist structure. It would be a direct attack on Federalism and it would overshadow the regional issues. When voting for national elections, we tend to choose parties that fulfill the dream of taking India forward globally as well as implementing policies at the National level. State governments are those that represent the people better, and fulfill their needs at a local level. Here we want someone who speaks our language, who comes from the same background and locality like us, and will be available more. Clubbing the two will make it difficult for people to know who does what. The essence of decentralization is to be truly decentralized, any centralization even for convenience ultimately erodes it. Another issue is the national parties are expected to have a strong position resulting either the state parties would join them or would be very less powerful. While the stated goal is efficiency, the real goal is control, easy governance, so the government can focus on issues and policies instead of focusing on elections, but in India it is the opposite. The government works when elections are near. However, if elections happen time and again, it puts pressure on the parties both at the center and at the state to perform diligently. It acts as a natural “checks and balances” on the government. We have elections every six months, although it is an expensive affair but it is good we have elections every six months, if the elections are held together every 5 years politicians will not even do that 1%, they are doing now and imagine not accountable for 5 years. It would not only be cost effective as well as the public resources and forces would be effectively managed. By consolidating elections, they’re trying to reduce the regular pulse-checks that the

public gets to administer through the voting machines. Right now, staggered elections ensure that the ruling party is held accountable for its actions throughout the year, with the public's voice being reflected in real-time, influenced by current events. Taking that away means insulating themselves from frequent electoral backlash. There is no easy solution to having too many elections but a solution that erodes federalism and democracy in even the slightest should be rejected straightaway.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Efficiency, Threat to Federalism, Accountability.*

ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS

SYNCHRONIZING DEMOCRACY: ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC DIMENSIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION IN INDIA

Manvi Singh⁶⁰

The idea of “One Nation, One Election”—synchronizing elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies—has emerged as a central debate in Indian democratic discourse. While constitutional, federal, and democratic issues form the core of this discussion, administrative and economic considerations present equally compelling dimensions that shape its feasibility. This paper examines the practical administrative challenges and economic implications of implementing a synchronized electoral system in India.

From an administrative standpoint, the conduct of elections in the world’s largest democracy is an extraordinary exercise involving the Election Commission of India, state machinery, security agencies, and civil services. Presently, India conducts elections almost every year, either for Parliament or State Assemblies, requiring recurring large-scale mobilization of resources—electronic voting machines (EVMs), Voter Verifiable Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT) units, polling personnel, and security forces. This repetitive deployment disrupts governance, diverts bureaucratic attention, and strains institutions. Synchronization could streamline election administration, reduce frequency of code of conduct impositions, and allow uninterrupted governance cycles. However, the administrative complexities of simultaneous elections—such as logistical management, ballot design for multiple levels of government, voter education, and safeguarding against malpractices—pose new challenges. Economically, recurrent elections impose significant costs on the exchequer and political parties alike. The Election Commission of India estimated the 2019 Lok Sabha election expenditure at over ₹60,000 crore (including both government and party spending). State-level elections add further to this burden. Frequent elections also lead to repeated imposition of the Model Code of Conduct, delaying policy decisions and government expenditure.

⁶⁰ Assistant Professor (Law), DPG Law College, Gurugram.

Synchronization promises cost efficiency by reducing redundancy in polling infrastructure, security deployment, and administrative preparation. It could also promote macroeconomic stability by minimizing electoral populism and fiscal disruptions caused by staggered election cycles. However, cost savings must be weighed against the initial investment required to overhaul infrastructure—mass procurement of EVMs, larger storage and training requirements, and enhanced digital safeguards. Drawing on comparative global experiences—from South Africa, Sweden, and Belgium—this paper highlights that synchronized elections can be administratively efficient and economically prudent if implemented with robust institutional design. Yet, India’s vast federal structure, diverse political landscape, and regional autonomy concerns require careful calibration. The feasibility of a “one-time” synchronization would depend on transitional mechanisms, constitutional amendments, and consensus-building across political stakeholders.

The paper argues that while One Nation, One Election may generate substantial administrative and economic efficiencies, it must not undermine democratic vibrancy or federal autonomy. Instead, a phased or partially synchronized model—such as clustering elections in zones or aligning state elections within a defined window—may offer a balanced approach. Ultimately, the initiative’s success rests on reconciling efficiency gains with India’s commitment to cooperative federalism and participatory democracy.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Administrative Efficiency, Governance, Federalism, Democratic Process.*

ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC STAKES OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION

Apoorv Mishra⁶¹ & Madhav Monga⁶²

The concept of “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) proposes synchronizing elections for the Lok Sabha, State Assemblies, and local bodies to streamline India’s electoral process. This reform aims to address the administrative inefficiencies and economic burdens associated with staggered elections, which disrupt governance and incur significant costs. By consolidating electoral cycles, ONOE seeks to reduce logistical redundancies, optimize resource utilization, and enhance voter engagement.

From an administrative perspective, ONOE offers substantial benefits. Synchronizing elections minimizes the repeated deployment of security forces, polling staff, and infrastructure, thereby reducing operational complexity. Countries like Brazil and Indonesia have demonstrated the feasibility of large-scale simultaneous elections, showcasing efficient use of electronic voting systems, polling stations, and trained personnel. For instance, Brazil’s centralized electoral model reduced costs per voter to just \$1.70, highlighting the potential for cost-effective election management. Similarly, Indonesia’s successful execution of simultaneous elections across its vast geography underscores the logistical viability of such reforms.

Economically, ONOE promises significant savings. India’s 2024 Lok Sabha elections alone cost ₹8,900 crore (~\$1.07 billion), reflecting the financial strain of frequent elections. Synchronizing electoral cycles could save India over ₹1 lakh crore in five years by consolidating expenditures on polling stations, election materials, and voter education campaigns. International case studies, such as Argentina’s Double Simultaneous Voting System (DSVS), further illustrate how aligning provincial and national elections can streamline processes and reduce costs.

⁶¹ Ph.D. Scholar, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁶² Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

Moreover, ONOE can mitigate election fatigue among voters and political parties, fostering higher voter turnout and focused campaigning. Countries like Belgium and Sweden have reported strong voter participation due to synchronized elections, with Belgium achieving a 90% turnout through mandatory voting and streamlined cycles. By reducing the frequency of elections, ONOE can enhance governance continuity, allowing policymakers to focus on long-term agendas rather than perpetual campaigning.

While challenges remain, particularly in safeguarding India's federal structure and accommodating its diversity, the administrative and economic advantages of ONOE make a compelling case for reform. Drawing from global best practices, ONOE represents a transformative approach to electoral management, promising efficiency, cost reduction, and strengthened democratic engagement.

Keywords: *ONOE, Administrative and Economic Advantages, Electoral Cycles, Synchronizing Elections.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: A MUCH-NEEDED REFORM?

Ankur Taya⁶³

In India, general elections for the House of the People and the State Legislative Assemblies were held simultaneously for the first four terms after independence. However, successive Central Governments started invoking constitutional provisions to dismiss state governments prematurely. With this frequent collapse of coalition governments at the state and central levels, the country began experiencing elections at different times throughout the year. After the 1967 Lok Sabha was dissolved, since then, it is seen that one or the other state has geared up for elections. Currently, on March 14th 2024, the High Level Committee, popularly known as the 'Kovind Panel', submitted its report on One Nation One Election (ONOE). The panel has recommended simultaneous elections to be held in 100 days. However, there are some challenges

⁶³ PhD Scholar, *Department of Laws, Panjab University, Chandigarh.*

in implementing the ONOE which have been aptly discussed in the report and the researchers would examine the submissions made in the report.

Starting with the concept of ONOE in the first part, the paper would briefly discuss the history behind the concept of simultaneous elections. In the next part, the researcher would analyse the Kovind Panel's submissions. Both the opposition to the ONOE and the benefits of having the ONOE would be discussed in the next part. The last part would be discussing the conclusions reached.

Keywords: *ONOE, elections, constitution, nation, democracy.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: ANALYSING ADMINISTRATIVE CONSTRAINT

*Bhavya Kapil*⁶⁴

India is the 'World's Largest Democracy'. With this title comes the practice of conducting elections throughout the country, multiple times. To bring down the frequency, the government has proposed 'One Nation One Election' which purports to synchronize the Lok Sabha and State Assembly elections, reducing electoral cost, refining governance and minimizing the disruption caused by the model code of conduct. In pursuit of these advantages, the government has overlooked the challenges that it brings. The paper aims to critically examine the administrative challenges including that of logistic challenges, voter management, security arrangements to be made for the elections, problems associated with resource allocation, determination of polling stations- which are usually educational institutions, would disrupt not just the administrative scenario but also demand compromise from educational sector for the time during which elections will be conducted, the cost might exacerbate the costs incurred during routine elections, etc. Other major administrative problems associated with the One Nation One Election are, that – although India has transformed itself to become digitally literate, the rural parts of the country

⁶⁴ LL.M, *Jamia Hamdard University, New Delhi.*

are yet to be familiarized with technological advancement. Elections rely heavily on voter awareness and rural set ups lack the same. And secondly, the amount of data that will be produced during elections will take a toll on technology-cum-management skills. These problems are likely to result in dismantling the democratic structure and rip apart the federal fabric of the country, thus redoing the structure into a web of complexities. In a vast country like India, conducting elections in the backdrop of ONOE doesn't seem to be a successful initiative. The paper, thus, assesses the viability of one nation one election, while considering the administrative constraints.

Keywords: *Administrative, Challenges, Democracy, Election, Federalism, Technology, Challenges.*

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: A COST–BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF ELECTORAL SYNCHRONIZATION IN THE WORLD'S LARGEST DEMOCRACY.

Swaraj Dash⁶⁵

The proposal of “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE), which seeks to synchronize elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies and Union Territories either on a single day or within a specific short time frame, has emerged as one of the most consequential yet contested debates in Indian electoral reforms. Though not yet implemented, ONOE has been widely discussed in parliamentary committees, policy think tanks, and the Election Commission of India as a measure to address the growing fiscal and administrative costs of India's electoral democracy. This paper undertakes a structured cost–benefit analysis of electoral synchronization in the world's largest democracy, with a particular focus on its potential economic implications. On the cost side, the study identifies the immense logistical and constitutional restructuring required to operationalize ONOE, ranging from simultaneous dissolution and extension of state legislatures to the harmonization of by-election mechanisms, alongside risks of undermining the

⁶⁵ Student, *XIM University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha.*

federal balance of power. It also highlights transitional uncertainties, including the administrative burden on electoral institutions and the possibility of political distortions during implementation. On the benefit side, the paper examines projected fiscal savings through reduced election expenditure by political parties, the Election Commission, and state machinery, drawing on data from past Lok Sabha and Assembly elections where expenditures have escalated significantly—from around ₹1,100 crore in the 2009 general elections to over ₹6,000 crore in 2019. The analysis suggests that synchronized elections could substantially reduce transaction costs, minimize disruptions caused by the frequent imposition of the Model Code of Conduct, and free up governance bandwidth for long-term policy implementation. Further, by mitigating the cycle of populist fiscal policies driven by staggered elections, ONOE could enhance macroeconomic stability and redirect public resources toward developmental priorities. However, the study cautions against overstating these benefits without addressing structural limitations and political economy trade-offs, particularly in a highly diverse federal democracy. The paper ultimately frames ONOE not merely as a logistical reform but as an economic policy debate, with profound implications for fiscal prudence, governance efficiency, and India's developmental trajectory toward Viksit Bharat@2047.

Keywords: *One Nation, One Election; ONOE; Electoral Synchronization; Political Economy of Elections; Fiscal Costs and Savings; Governance Efficiency; Electoral Finance.*

THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF DEMOCRACY: ENVIRONMENTAL ECONOMICS OF ELECTORAL CYCLES

Khushbu Yadav⁶⁶

This research shines a light on an often-neglected aspect of democracy: its environmental cost. By comparing India's familiar practice of holding elections at different times with a single, countrywide vote under the One Nation, One Election (ONOE) proposal, the study calculates the

⁶⁶ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University, Sonapat.*

total carbon emissions each system produces. Instead of debating only legal and administrative issues, it brings in environmental economics to ask a fresh question: how sustainable are our voting processes? Measuring everything from campaign travel and polling-station energy use to ballot-paper production and waste disposal, this work treats the carbon footprint as a vital indicator of an electoral system's actual impact. In doing so, it offers a new perspective on electoral reform, one that places ecological responsibility alongside constitutional and governance considerations.

Employing a Life Cycle Assessment methodology, the analysis captures CO₂ equivalent emissions across all phases of election conduct. Campaigning activities contribute considerable transportation emissions due to candidates, party workers, and supporters travelling the country to conduct rallies and door-knocking. The administrative system uses energy to send out electronic voting machines, operate counting centres, and manage polling places. The act of voting generates further emissions due to the travel of electors to polling places via public bus systems, vehicles, or shared transport. Each election cycle also requires significant material inputs, including ballot papers, posters, flags, handbills, and other items, all of which need to be produced, shipped, and ultimately discarded, collectively increasing the carbon footprint of the election.

Data were sourced from logistics records for the Election Commission, procurement records, transport audits from the transport-related task forces, and records on municipal solid waste management. An econometric model then connects these data sources to model total emissions over approximately five years (the length of a complete term). The results indicate that in India's staggered elections, overall estimated emissions are about 1.8 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent. If all the polls were conducted as one event, emissions were in the range of 0.9-1.1 million tonnes. This reduction in emissions is attributed to several factors: the transportation of election-related materials in a single day, lower costs associated with bulk procurement, shorter election administration times, and fewer days spent in compliance with the Model Code of Conduct. Sensitivity analyses further reveal that adopting virtual campaign events and online voter engagement platforms could deepen these reductions by up to 60%.

Given this evidence, the study proposes the following steps: employing required carbon audits in every election campaign plan, enforcing green procurement criteria on goods supplied for electoral campaigns, implementing carbon-offsetting specifications for political parties on a proportional basis to their emissions incurred during their campaign, and promoting digital campaign dispositional strategies that promote low physical materials. By aligning environmental economics with electoral reform, this research is a substantial contribution to the nascent field of green political science. It also provides a compelling framework for democracies around the world to embed better practice electoral systems in line with climate goals.

Keywords: *Carbon footprint, Life Cycle Assessment, One Nation, One Election (ONOE), Environmental Economics, Electoral cycles, Green political science.*

THE COST OF DEMOCRACY: ADMINISTRATIVE AND FINANCIAL DIMENSIONS OF ELECTIONS IN INDIA

Mritunjay Kumar Mishra⁶⁷

The conduct of elections in the world's largest democracy is both a massive job to India's democratic strength and a challenge of huge scale. Concerns regarding the administrative and financial challenges of the current election cycle have been in the ongoing discussion regarding simultaneous elections, which are commonly referred to as "One Nation, One Election" (ONOE). Regular elections improve accountability and maintain government responsiveness, but they also result in large financial spending, put a burden on the administrative system, and cause governance to be disrupted by the Model Code of Conduct's regular implementation. This paper evaluates the cost of democracy in India with an emphasis on the administrative and fiscal dimensions of elections. It examines constitutional, governmental, and practical issues while analyzing the possible advantages and disadvantages of synchronized elections. The research shows that simultaneous elections run the risk of undermining federal autonomy and narrowing

⁶⁷ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University, Sonapat.*

the scope for regional political expression., even though they may also improve administrative efficiency and prevent duplication of spending. The paper makes the case for a careful, progressive approach to election reform that strikes a balance between efficiency and democratic pluralism by focusing on concrete evidence and comparative viewpoints. Ultimately, the cost of democracy cannot be measured only in monetary terms; it also depends on how well it maintains responsibility, representation, and participation in a diverse nation like India.

Keywords: *constitutional, governmental, elections, political, comparative, democracy.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION IN INDIA: NAVIGATING THROUGH ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC CHALLENGES

Navin Pal Singh⁶⁸

India is a union of 28 States and 8 Union Territories having a total population of 1450 million. As per the 2024 General Election's official date presented by Election Commission of India, 977.9 million citizens are registered voters in India. During the 2024 General Elections, out of 977.9 million electors, 642.1 million electors exercised their right of vote. Conducting General Elections at central level and State Assembly elections in the world's largest democracy i.e. India, is a mammoth task. This process of conducting various elections in India becomes more challenging as every year on average. 5 to 6 State Assembly elections take place every year. Such frequent elections in India not only puts a huge financial burden on the public exchequer's fund but also creates a situation of policy paralysis as all development related activities come to halt till the time the Model Code of Conduct remains in force.

In order to make India's electoral system more efficient, the NDA led central government has put forward the idea of 'One Nation One Election' (ONOE) in India to hold elections for the Lok Sabha, state legislative assemblies, and maybe even local bodies all at the same time. This paper

⁶⁸ Ph.D. Research Scholar, *Maharaja Surajmal Brij University, Bharatpur, Rajasthan.*

not only looks at the history of simultaneous elections, critically analysing various advantages of simultaneous elections but also throws light on administrative and economic problems that may come with the implementation of One Nation One Election. It talks about the problems with logistics, the need for resources, the worries about federalism, and the effects on the budget.

Keywords: *Simultaneous Elections, One Nation One Election (ONOE) Electoral Reforms, Federalism, Democratic Governance, Administrative Challenges, Electoral Expenditure, Policy Paralysis*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION

Aditya Sahu⁶⁹ & Akshit Broka

India, the world's largest and most vibrant democracy, has an exuberant electoral process. Yet, this very democratic process often comes at a staggering cost. The 2024 Lok Sabha elections alone witnessed an expenditure of nearly 1.35 lakh crore—a figure so huge that it understandably raises eyebrows among well-aware citizens. With one election or another occurring almost every year—be it national, state, or local—the nation finds itself in a perpetual campaign mode, straining both its logistics and its administrative machinery. It is in this context that the idea of "One Nation, One Election" emerges not merely as a political convenience rather it's the need of the hour. By synchronising our electoral cycles, we would not only streamline the logistical web that currently burdens our Election Commission, but also mitigate the colossal expenditure that recurrent elections inevitably entail. Yet, the proposal does not come without its challenges. Constitutional amendments would be required to balance terms of elected bodies, political consensus would be essential in the diverse interests of states and questions about mid-term dissolutions or emergency situations would need careful resolution. Detractors also argue that the simultaneous nature of elections may suppress regional interests in the face of dominant national narratives. These are legitimate concerns that must be addressed with institutional safeguards to

⁶⁹ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

ensure that democratic pluralism is not compromised. In essence, the call for simultaneous elections is not an attempt to degrade democracy, but rather an endeavour to preserve its efficiency, sustainability, and sanctity. It represents an attempt to recalibrate our democratic process so that it is less about endless campaigning and more about consistent governance. By synchronising electoral cycles, India would be able to save vast financial resources, reduce the administrative fatigue and provide governments the stability required for meaningful policy implementation.

Keywords: *policy, democratic pluralism, simultaneous elections, elected bodies.*

ADMINISTRATIVE AND ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: TOWARDS ENHANCED GOVERNANCE AND FISCAL EFFICIENCY

Vinay Kumar Lakhlan⁷⁰ & Diksha Kumari⁷¹

The proposal of "One Nation, One Election" represents a significant paradigm shift in India's electoral and governance landscape, promising profound administrative and economic repercussions for the world's largest democracy. This paper critically analyses the administrative and economic dimensions of synchronizing elections for the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies, as reflected in the Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-ninth Amendment) Bill, 2024. From an administrative perspective, frequent and staggered elections disrupt governance continuity, divert crucial resources, and strain India's extensive bureaucratic machinery. The recurring deployment of security forces, repurposing of educational institutions as polling stations, and preoccupation of senior officials with election duties hamstring developmental activities. Simultaneous elections, therefore, offer an avenue to enhance administrative efficiency by consolidating electoral operations, reducing overlaps, and enabling departments to concentrate on sustained policy execution. The phased implementation recommended by the High-Level

⁷⁰ Student, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.

⁷¹ Student, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.

Committee chaired by Shri Ram Nath Kovind seeks to ensure smooth transition and adaptability of administrative frameworks, overcoming logistical and procedural bottlenecks that may arise in aligning election cycles across 28 states and 8 union territories.

Economically, elections in India entail substantial public expenditure, encompassing not just polling and security costs but also incidental expenses owing to restrictions under the Model Code of Conduct. Multiple elections throughout the year perpetuate fiscal drain and inertia in infrastructural and welfare projects. By synchronizing election schedules, the government can realize considerable savings through the consolidation of resources, curtailment of duplicated expenditure, and rationalization of campaign logistics. This convergence further minimizes interruptions in public works and policy execution, bolstering consistent economic activity and enabling judicious allocation of funds towards developmental priorities. Additionally, the reduced frequency of populist spending can impart greater fiscal discipline to India's budgetary processes, preventing unplanned and ad hoc outlays associated with electoral cycles.

The potential for systemic improvement is considerable; yet, the shift towards "One Nation, One Election" must cautiously navigate challenges of constitutional propriety, federal balance, and practical feasibility. Transition strategies must prioritize infrastructure readiness, capacity-building of Election Commission and state bodies, and phased adaptations to safeguard the democratic vibrancy and inclusion of varied regional contexts. Stakeholder consultations, comparative perspectives, and empirical evaluations must inform operational models, ensuring administrative coherence and economic sustainability. In sum, the synchronisation of elections could revolutionize India's governance and fiscal landscape by streamlining administrative functions and maximizing economic efficiencies. While the envisioned benefits are substantial, they are contingent upon meticulous planning, constitutional robustness, and a commitment to maintaining the integrity of India's federal and democratic ethos.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Administrative Efficiency, Electoral Expenditure, Governance, Economic Impact, Policy Transition.*

VOTER ENGAGEMENT AND DEMOCRATIC PARTICIPATION

ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION: AN AGENDA FOR ELECTORAL REFORMS IN INDIA

Nisha⁷² & Lakshay⁷³

The debate on “One Nation, One Election” has re-emerged as a crucial issue in India’s democratic discourse. This is not a new concept as after the adoption of the Constitution, the elections to Lok Sabha and all State Legislative Assemblies were held simultaneously from 1951 till 1967 but from 1967 onwards India saw a lot of Political Instability. For instance, in the 1967 elections the Congress party lost control in several states like Bihar, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh, these states either saw non- Congress parties or coalitions coming to power. One Nation, One Tax, One Nation, One Ration Card, and One Nation, One Subscription together symbolise India’s move towards greater unity in policy and governance.

Almost 80% of the population is in favour of simultaneous elections. The central motive is to move beyond the administrative and economic arguments surrounding electoral synchronisation and to interrogate its impact on voter engagement and democratic participation. The main objective is to cut down election costs, ensure smooth flow of development work and minimise disruptions caused by the elections. India will overcome the inefficiency of Model Code of Conduct (MCC) which comes into force with the announcement of poll dates, prevents the government from announcing any new scheme, making any new appointments, transfer, postings without the approval of Election Commission, which brings the normal work of government to a standstill.

This paper explores the concept from multiple perspectives. It examines the historical background of simultaneous elections in India, analyses the potential advantages such as Reduced Electoral Expenditure, Streamlined Governance, Increased Voter Participation, and Minimization of Administrative Fatigue. At the same time, it critically assesses the challenges,

⁷² Research Scholar, *Department of Laws, Panjab University.*

⁷³ Junior Research Fellow, *Department of Laws, Panjab University.*

including federal concerns, constitutional hurdles, and the possibility of state governments losing autonomy.

The study further discusses whether “One Nation, One Election” can serve as a unifying reform for democratic stability or whether it risks centralizing power and undermining the spirit of federalism. The paper concludes with constructive suggestions aimed at balancing electoral efficiency with democratic inclusivity, thereby providing a detailed assessment of whether this policy could be a miracle or a disaster for India’s democracy.

Keywords: *Simultaneous Elections, Model Code of Conduct, Electoral Expenditure, Governance Stability, Democratic Participation.*

THE SILENT CONSTITUENCY: WHY STUDENTS MUST BE CENTRAL TO THE ONE DEBATE

*Somesh Rai*⁷⁴

The debate on One Nation, One Election (ONOE) is often done around efficiency, costs, logistical feasibility and questions of federalism. But in this conversation, one constituency has been consistently overlooked “student voters” who are pursuing their education outside their home states. Under the current legal framework on elections, voting is tied to the residential status of an individual. Unlike defence personnel or people in service of the union, students are excluded from ballot based absentee voting facilities. As a result, whenever exams clash with polling days, many young voters are practically shut out of the democratic process. Considering that the 18–25 age group is the single largest pool of new voters, this exclusion directly undermines the principle of universal adult suffrage under Article 326. This paper adopting a reformist approach argues that ONOE, instead of worsening such disenfranchisement, actually offers India a valuable chance to rethink and redesign the absentee voting framework. Looking at comparative practices from countries like the UK, US, and Australia where students can use

⁷⁴ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

postal or advance voting, or maintain a dual registration it is clear that innovation and inclusivity can go hand in hand with electoral integrity. The recent push by the Election Commission to test Remote Voting Machines (RVMs) for migrant workers provides further grounds to extend similar arrangements for students, perhaps through Aadhaar based verification or biometric safeguards. Naturally, questions about fraud, coercion, and the larger need to protect free and fair elections remain. As cases like *PUCL v. Union of India* (2003) reminds us of the need to uphold democracy at all times. Yet, the real threat is not reform but the continued exclusion of mobile young student voters. The marginal risks of trying new methods are far outweighed by the democratic costs of keeping this “silent constituency” on the sidelines. To conclude, ONOE cannot be called a complete reform unless it makes room for students in the voting framework. That means formally recognising them as a category of absentee voters, experimenting with postal or remote voting, and ensuring electoral schedules do not consistently clash with academic calendars. ONOE should not just mean holding elections together; it must mean expanding the circle of participation so that India’s youngest voices are present, counted, and heard.

ELECTORAL CONTINUITY AND STABILITY VS. VOTER AUTONOMY: DOCTRINAL CONFLICTS IN THE ONE DEBATE

Ishita Jawa⁷⁵ & Vaibhav Khanna⁷⁶

“Political democracy cannot last unless there lies at the base of it social democracy.” — Dr. B.R. Ambedkar

The debate on “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) brings to the forefront a nuanced constitutional and democratic dilemma in India: balancing electoral continuity and systemic stability with preserving voter autonomy and democratic responsiveness. ONOE promises to streamline electoral schedules, reduce disruptions, and foster governance stability. However, it

⁷⁵ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University*.

⁷⁶ Student, *IIMT, GGSIP University, Delhi*.

also risks compressing electoral cycles and undermining the distinct mandates that voters issue to their representatives, potentially jeopardizing robust democratic accountability.

This study carefully examines these doctrinal conflicts within the constitutional framework provided by seminal Supreme Court judgments such as *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973) and *S.R. Bommai v. Union of India* (1994), which articulates the principles protecting electoral periodicity, federal balance, and representative governance. Unlike earlier administrative or political analyses, this research integrates constitutional theory, empirical electoral behavior, and federal dynamics to critically assess ONOE's implications.

Filling a vital research gap, the paper argues that ONOE should not be treated solely as an exercise in political synchronization but as a constitutional project demanding safeguards preserving voter autonomy and subnational diversity. It concludes by outlining principles and institutional reforms necessary to reconcile stability with democratic plurality, embedding ONOE within constitutional morality and the lived realities of India's federal democracy.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Electoral Continuity, Voter Autonomy, Constitutional Doctrine, Federalism, Democratic Accountability.*

A CRITICAL RESEARCH REVIEW ON THE POTENTIAL IMPACT OF ONE NATION AND ONE ELECTION: THE VOTER'S PERSPECTIVE

*Ishita Anand*⁷⁷

The Electoral System is one of the sensitive yet essential features of any country. Elections play a significant role in the governance of our country. The right to vote is a citizen's duty towards strengthening Indian democracy. An electoral reform of one nation, one election may bring about a change in their rights and perception. The present paper tries to analyse the potential impacts of simultaneous election pan India. With the help of research reviews, this paper tries to understand

⁷⁷ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

the pros and cons of such an electoral reform on the voters. This study tries to examine the logistics, implications and challenges of voter participation in such a harmonized electoral system. It also discusses the impact of one nation, one election on budgeting, time management, electoral cycles and administration. With a focus on the diverse set of countries, the current study aims to understand the implications of the current electoral reform on the voters' engagement through an emphasis on their unique federal system. The study tries to collect information and relevant data with the help of literature reviews. The present paper will have significant implications in understanding the positive influence and potential drawbacks of synchronised election systems. The findings of the study can serve as a platform for further discussion on continuity of such policies, constitutional liberty and subjugation as well political strategies. It also contributes towards analysing the psychological influence and inclination of the eligible voters of our country. The present paper suggests several scopes for future research. It also suggests certain preventive measures that can reduce the concerns related to voter fatigue, negligence of democratic practices like testing the confidence of the government and playing with the present electoral systems of India.

Keywords: *Electoral System, Voters participation, federal system, democratic practices, Budgeting.*

PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACTS OF ELECTORAL SYNCHRONIZATION ON VOTER BEHAVIOUR

Piyush⁷⁸ & Saksham Singh⁷⁹

Elections are important for functioning of democracy; especially the mechanism of conducting elections shapes the political, social and other related factors in the policy making and functioning of the country. In elections the voter behaviour such as voter turnout, cognitive burden, decision making and other things are crucial for electoral practices.

⁷⁸ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁷⁹ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

The presentation of the 129th Constitutional Amendment Bill has started the discussions over the simultaneous elections also known as “One Nation One Election” in India. The proposed changes in the mechanism of conducting elections in the country will influence a common voter; especially the voter behaviour which is the guiding factor of the election process. In this paper we will be assessing the psychological effects on the voters’ behaviour in the synchronized election process.

To prepare our writings we have adopted a doctrinal research of different research papers based on empirical and non-empirical data to lead findings of different impacts on voter behaviour. Here we have highlighted that in the case of the simultaneous elections of different governments there has been an increase in the voter turnout, reduction in ‘voter-fatigue’, collective motivation for ‘election day’; but on other hand there are concerns as cognitive burden of voter due to increase in information, shadowing of the regional issues under the national issues, chances of increase in anti-incumbency, increase in influence of larger parties due to ‘coattail effect’ which seek urgent action to resolve for curbing any post implementation challenges.

In this paper we have proposed certain solutions such as spreading voter awareness, voter education programmes, policies to create space for regional issues to be highlighted in front of voters and others. The psychological impacts on the voters must be studied to mitigate the risks, uphold the values of fairness, equality and preserve the faith of citizens of India in the democratic process.

Keywords: *Voter Behaviour, Electoral Synchronisation, cognitive burden, psychological impact, Simulation elections.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION WITH INCLUSIVE PARTICIPATION

*Pragya*⁸⁰

Elections are a major event in India, it not only tests people's faith in the political institution but also a platform to represent their perspective on a large scale. During a press conference for Lok Sabha elections of 2024 former Chief Election Commissioner of India Mr. Rajiv Kumar said "The daunting challenges in conducting free and fair elections are four-fold, 4 Ms: Muscles, Money, Misinformation and Model Code of Conduct (MCC) violations." He then added that the ECI is committed and has put in place measures to deal with these disruptive challenges. One Nation, One Election or simultaneous elections is that way to mitigate those challenges and can help in conducting elections effectively. The stakes of the whole nation depend upon elections makes it a topic of immense research . It is crucial to know where our resources are going and whether it is being utilized properly or not. Voter participation has decreased from 67% in 2019 to 65.79% in 2025 in Lok Sabha elections, which is not what could be expected from a vibrant and flourishing country like India. According to 2024 data there are 744 political parties in India and out of which only 6 are national parties, 258 are state parties and the rest 680 are parties not reflecting in results of elections. For research paper data from various articles and journals will be used. To support the perspective, statistics from national and international sources will be analysed. Government reports and testimonies of political leaders and dignitaries would be the primary data. The paper's approach will be to explore why and how O.N.O.E has become a potential necessity. Its impact on effectiveness and functionality of democratic institutions of India, especially the political one. Brief about the nature of voters, their perspective and behavioural pattern over the time. It will aim at the analysis that, whether democracy can survive in such an environment of One Nation One Election? and whether it will strengthen voter participation or not.

Keywords: *ONOE, democracy, ECI, political, voter participation.*

⁸⁰ Student, *Dr.BR Ambedkar National Law University.*

UNIFORMITY AT WHAT COST? RETHINKING ELECTORAL REFORM AMIDST FEDERALISM AND INSTITUTIONAL TRUST DEFICITS

*Mehak Marodia*⁸¹

The recommendation of “One Nation, One Election” indicates distinctly aspiring electoral reforms in post-independence India, deepening constitutional, federal, and democratic questions. While the government proclaims that synchronised elections will restrain electoral expenditure and administrative disruptions, the argument is increasingly complex. Historically, there were simultaneous elections from 1952–1967, which collapsed due to premature dissolutions under Articles 352 and 356, punctuating the risks of central overreach. A study found that when elections are held simultaneously, 77% of voters chose the same party at both national and state levels (compared to 61% under staggered polls). This trend strengthens national parties but weakens regional voices. So there’s a great challenge for sustaining the integrity and diversity of the nation. However, smaller nations like Sweden and South Africa, with centralized institutions and homogenous electorates, have successfully run synchronised elections. But India has certain challenges having a diverse population. This paper hypothesizes that while synchronised elections may attain short-term cost efficiency and administrative order, they endanger scraping the federal fabric of Indian democracy. India being a land of diversity makes the plan of One Nation, One Election impractical, but its goals—decreasing costs and solidifying governance—are worth pursuing. Instead of forcing uniformity, reforms must respect federalism and democracy. At the same time, debates like the Uniform Civil Code (Article 44) and concerns over the Election Commission’s independence in 2025 underscore the consequences of centralizing reforms without consensus. Article 324 mandates an impartial Commission, but accusations of voter roll tampering—such as allegations over Special Intensive Revision in Bihar and claims of electoral exclusion have swayed public faith. With voter turnout sinking to 65.79% in 2024 from 67.1% in 2019. The tentative outcome of my study is that India must pursue

⁸¹ Student, *University Institute of Legal Studies, Panjab University, Chandigarh.*

electoral reform that preserves federalism and pluralism. A feasible way lies in transformative reforms—cluster-based election cycles, renegotiated MCC protocols via ECI-led multiparty dialogue, robust digital transparency tools, and precise campaign funding limits. Thus, the actual challenge is not enforcing uniformity but constructing reforms that magnify efficiency while shielding the democratic and federal spirit of the Constitution.

Keywords: *Pluralism, Diversity, Democratic fabric, Federalism, Electoral reforms, Model Code of Conduct*

ONE NATION AND ONE ELECTION

Akhil Chauhan⁸² & Priyanshu Chunbouk⁸³

The "One Nation, One Election" proposal in India has sparked a significant debate about voter engagement and democratic participation. This idea aims to synchronize all elections in the country, from the Lok Sabha to state assemblies, with the goal of improving the electoral process. Supporters argue that holding elections simultaneously would simplify governance, cut election-related costs, and increase economic efficiency. One of the main benefits of One Nation, One Election is higher voter turnout. By holding elections together, voters would be more involved, potentially leading to a turnout of about 90%. This would ensure that more citizens participate in the democratic process, making it more representative and inclusive. Additionally, simultaneous elections would cut down on election fatigue, allowing governments to focus on their responsibilities instead of constantly preparing for elections. This would help them implement policies and development projects more effectively.

The economic benefits of One Nation, One Election are also significant. Estimates suggest that simultaneous elections could boost India's GDP by 1.5-1.6%, which amounts to ₹4.5 lakh crore. This funding could be invested in key areas like education and health, resulting in better

⁸² Student, *Dr. BR Ambedkar National University, Sonapat.*

⁸³ Student, *Dr. BR Ambedkar National University, Sonapat.*

outcomes and an improved quality of life for citizens. With fewer elections, governments could focus on implementing policies and development activities, leading to better governance and more effective public service delivery.

However, putting One Nation, One Election into practice would require substantial resources, including staff, security, and electronic voting machines. The logistical challenges would be considerable, and the Election Commission would need to invest heavily in new electronic voting machines, estimated at ₹10,000 crore every 15 years. Moreover, the proposal faces opposition from various parties, who argue it could weaken India's federal structure and lead to authoritarianism. Some also believe that simultaneous elections could put regional parties at a disadvantage, allowing national parties to dominate the electoral scene.

Despite these challenges, the Indian government has taken up the proposal and created a high level committee, led by former President Ram Nath Kovind, to review the feasibility of simultaneous elections. The committee's recommendations would create a basis for implementing One Nation, One Election and help address some concerns raised by opposition parties. A joint parliamentary committee has also been formed to discuss the proposal and offer recommendations.

In conclusion, One Nation, One Election is a complex proposal that needs careful consideration of its benefits and challenges. While it may improve voter engagement, lessen election fatigue, and enhance economic efficiency, it also brings significant logistical and constitutional issues. Ultimately, the success of this proposal will depend on its implementation and the ability of the government and the Election Commission to tackle the concerns raised by various groups. If executed well, One Nation, One Election could lead to a more efficient electoral process, benefiting India's democracy.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, Economic benefits, Voter Engagement, Logistical Challenges.*

THE HEGEMONY OF SYNCHRONY: EVM FRAGILITY, FEDERAL FAULTLINES, AND INDIA'S RISK OF DOMESTIC COLD WAR UNDER ONE

Anup Kumar Yadav⁸⁴ & Harsh Srivastava⁸⁵

One Nation, One Election (ONOE) has been presented as an institutional reform to increase efficiency and decrease electoral costs. India's democratic experience, however, shows that such convergence threatens electoral integrity and constitutional equilibrium. Indeed, the 2024 Lok Sabha elections, already extended over seven phases in an attempt to manage Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs), security deployment, and polling staff, highlight the logistical vulnerability of the system. In a synchronised framework, any failure or opacity in the operation of EVMs would have national ramifications, thereby jeopardising the legitimacy of electoral results and paving the way for the consolidation of power by a single group. The refusal to release the CCTV surveillance footage and unresolved discrepancies in the electoral rolls have already eroded public confidence, casting grave doubts on the transparency and accountability of the electoral process. Contemporary debates suggest that ONOE may further weaken India's federal architecture by subordinating state-specific issues to a national narrative, compromising state autonomy, and giving preference to national parties over regional formations. Experience from Indonesia, where holding simultaneous elections (*pilkada serentak*) created voter fatigue, centralisation effects and logistical strain, before the Constitutional Court mandated its return to staggered cycles from 2029, emphasises the dangers of a rush to re-engineer institutions before the right time. India's own record of simultaneous elections between 1951 and 1967 snapped in view of premature dissolutions, exposing the vulnerability of synchrony in a coalition-inclined polity. Jurisprudentially, ONOE would entail changes to Articles 83 and 174 of the Constitution, amendments to the Representation of the People Act, and thorough interaction with the Basic

⁸⁴ Student, *Vivekananda Institute of Professional Studies, Delhi*

⁸⁵ Student, *Vivekananda Institute of Professional Studies, Delhi.*

Structure doctrine, which brings into question the allowable boundaries of constitutional engineering.

In this paper, we highlight a research gap of the lack of interrogation of the reliability of the EVM, the transparency of the chain of custody and the constitutional implications of electoral synchronisation. The challenges are both legal and democratic: levelling the playing field, preserving federal pluralism and electoral legitimacy. The paper argues that in the absence of institutional strengthening, independent auditing and jurisprudential clarity, ONOE risks institutionalising opacity and entrenching hegemonic domination. Accordingly, it makes recommendations for phased experimentation with partial synchrony, the rise of independent EVM audit mechanisms, and constitutional protections for the autonomy of the state and pluralistic representation. Only such calibrated measures will ensure that reform complements rather than disturbs India's democratic balance.

Keywords: *EVM, Contemporary, Hegemony, Centralisation, Preference.*

ONE NATION ONE ELECTION

Radhika Chawla⁸⁶ & Varma Khushi⁸⁷

Elections have long been the representative of democracy, tracing back to ancient Greece and now to the whole world it has continued to act as a vital mechanism for ensuring people's participation in governance. In India, however, the frequency and scale of elections place an immense financial and administrative burden on the state resources that could otherwise be allocated to development have been allotted to fund elections. The concept of One Nation, One Election (ONOE) emerges as a proposed solution to this recurring challenge, advocating for synchronised elections across all tiers of government: central, state, and local.

⁸⁶ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁸⁷ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

This paper examines the ONOE proposal through legal, administrative, and democratic lenses. Our idea to write this paper arises from the question whether this reform enhances governance efficiency and Sustainable public finance or poses risks to India's federal structure and regional representation. The sources like Law Commission's 2018 Draft Report, the 79th Parliamentary Standing Committee Report (2015), and NITI Aayog's analysis helped to investigate both the potential benefits such as stable tenures and improved policymaking and the significant logistical and constitutional challenges and the legal aspect of dealing with amendments in Articles 83(2) and 172(1) of the Constitution. While ensuring representation for the masses is fundamental to a democracy, it must not impose an excessive financial strain on the state ultimately borne by taxpayers. At the same time, any reform intended to reduce this burden must not compromise the federal spirit enshrined in the Indian Constitution.

Furthermore, looking at the logistical aspect the paper reflects on operational feasibility corresponding to EVMs and VPATs, compared to the Election Commission's current capacity. The viability of One Nation, One Election ultimately rests on the ability to forge the political consensus, enact comprehensive legal reforms, and strike a delicate balance between national cohesion and preserving the constitutional autonomy of the states. This paper raises a critical question that despite the numerous implementation challenges, can the concept of One Nation, One Election remain a viable reform that strengthens democratic governance without infringing upon the basic structure of the Constitution?

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, electoral reform, Indian democracy, federalism, constitutional amendment, simultaneous elections, governance, voter behaviour, election expenditure, NITI Aayog.*

COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES

SYNCHRONIZING ELECTIONS IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CONSTITUTIONAL, FEDERAL, AND DEMOCRATIC CHALLENGES

*Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar*⁸⁸

The idea of “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) has emerged as a significant electoral reform debate in India. It proposes synchronizing elections to the Lok Sabha and all State Legislative Assemblies so that voters cast their ballots once every five years for both tiers of government. Advocates argue that this system would reduce the financial burden of frequent elections, minimize disruptions caused by repeated implementation of the Model Code of Conduct, and foster a more stable governance environment. Opponents, however, caution that ONOE raises profound constitutional, federal, and democratic challenges that demand careful examination before adoption. This paper critically explores the constitutional requirements, federal implications, and democratic consequences of implementing ONOE, highlighting the balance between efficiency and the spirit of India’s plural democracy.

Constitutionally, India currently operates on a system that permits variable electoral cycles because both the Lok Sabha and State Assemblies can be dissolved before completing their five-year tenure under Articles 83 and 172 of the Constitution. Implementing ONOE would therefore require significant constitutional amendments, particularly regarding Articles 83, 85, 172, 174, and 356, to synchronize terms and address contingencies such as premature dissolution or imposition of President’s Rule. Furthermore, judicial interpretations of free and fair elections as part of the basic structure of the Constitution (*Kesavananda Bharati*, *Indira Gandhi v. Raj Narain*, and *People’s Union for Civil Liberties* cases) raise questions about whether ONOE enhances or diminishes electoral freedom. While ONOE may streamline election management, its compatibility with the doctrine of basic structure must be carefully tested.

⁸⁸ Student, *Central University of Haryana*.

From a federal perspective, ONOE challenges the delicate balance between the Union and the States. India's Constitution, though quasi-federal, grants autonomy to states through elected legislatures with separate electoral mandates. Forcing simultaneous elections risks undermining this autonomy, as the national narrative could overshadow regional issues, thereby weakening federalism. Critics argue that regional parties might lose space in the homogenizing effect of synchronized elections, leading to centralization of power. Additionally, aligning electoral cycles would require either curtailing or extending the tenure of certain legislatures, which could be seen as an encroachment on state rights. Proponents, however, suggest that synchronized elections can strengthen cooperative federalism by reducing electoral friction between the Centre and States, ensuring policy continuity, and preventing frequent policy paralysis caused by political calculations around staggered elections.

Democratically, ONOE poses both opportunities and risks. On the one hand, frequent elections increase voter fatigue, escalate campaign spending, and divert administrative machinery from governance to election management. Simultaneous elections could reduce these costs, free resources for development, and promote stability. On the other hand, democracy is not only about efficiency but also about ensuring representation of diverse voices. Critics contend that ONOE might dilute electoral accountability by reducing opportunities for voters to periodically express dissatisfaction. Moreover, synchronized elections could privilege national issues over local concerns, undermining the representative character of state legislatures. Research also suggests that simultaneous elections may create a "coattail effect," where national-level political trends disproportionately influence state level outcomes, weakening the federal democratic fabric.

Practically, implementing ONOE requires robust institutional mechanisms. The Election Commission of India (ECI) would need to ensure logistical capacity, including electronic voting machines, personnel deployment, and security arrangements at unprecedented scale. Mechanisms to address mid-term instability, such as constructive votes of no-confidence, caretaker governments, or fixed tenures, would be essential. International experiences, particularly from South Africa, Sweden, and Germany, show that synchronized elections can work, but these countries operate within different constitutional and political frameworks. Thus, India's context

of coalition politics, linguistic diversity, and regional aspirations necessitates a tailored model rather than a mechanical transplant.

In conclusion, ONOE presents a complex reform proposal with constitutional, federal, and democratic dimensions. While the idea promises efficiency, cost reduction, and political stability, it simultaneously raises concerns about erosion of federal autonomy, distortion of democratic accountability, and weakening of representational pluralism. Any move towards ONOE must therefore be preceded by wide consultation across political parties, states, and civil society, alongside careful constitutional design to safeguard federalism and democracy. Rather than a wholesale shift, a phased or partial synchronization—such as clustering elections into two or three cycles—may balance efficiency with constitutional and democratic values. Ultimately, the debate on ONOE reflects the tension between governance efficiency and democratic pluralism in India's constitutional order, making it one of the most significant electoral reform discussions of our time.

REVISITING SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION AND GLOBAL ELECTORAL MODELS

Vikas Man Singh⁸⁹ & Radha⁹⁰

India's discussion of "One Nation, One Election" (ONOE) is representative of a larger international discussion on electoral synchronization that is occurring in nations like Belgium, South Africa, and Sweden. Up until 1967, when early dissolutions broke the pattern, India also held simultaneous elections for the State Assemblies and Lok Sabha. In light of comparative lessons learned from other democracies that have attempted or institutionalized synchronized elections, a thorough constitutional and federal examination is necessary to revive this paradigm in the modern period.

⁸⁹ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁹⁰ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

This study compares the theoretical approaches to electoral synchronization in a few democracies, including Canada, Sweden, Germany, and South Africa, with additional perspectives from Belgium, Indonesia, the US, and Latin America. These international experiences bring to light both benefits and difficulties. Belgium is a prime example of efficiency and cost savings through proportional representation and compulsory voting, while Sweden and South Africa show how fixed-term synchronized elections can increase voter involvement and simplify governance. On the other hand, federal systems like the United States and Germany maintain staggered cycles to protect state autonomy, and the 2019 election in Indonesia highlights the serious logistical hazards of large-scale synchronization.

To implement ONOE in India, significant constitutional adjustments to Articles 83, 85, 172, 174, and 356 would be required, in addition to state ratification under Article 368(2). While supporters highlight cost savings and policy stability, critics warn that holding elections at the same time could weaken federalism, stifle local voices, and consolidate political power. In order to balance efficiency and federal flexibility, the Election Commission of India and several expert bodies, including the Law Commission, Parliamentary Standing Committee, NITI Aayog, and Kovind Committee, have suggested phased or hybrid arrangements.

Although ONOE provides administrative and financial benefits, the study comes to the conclusion that its implementation in India needs to be gradual, led by agreement, and backed by robust constitutional protections. According to comparative lessons, in order to maintain stability and responsiveness, reforms should reinforce democratic accountability, respect India's federal diversity, and incorporate tools like a constructive vote of no confidence.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election (ONOE), Simultaneous Elections, Electoral Synchronisation Federalism, Constitutional Amendments, Election Commission of India (ECI), Governance Stability, Voter Participation, Comparative Doctrinal Study.*

CONSTITUTIONAL VIABILITY OF ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: COMPARATIVE STUDY WITH FEDERAL DEMOCRACIES AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN INDIA

Srishty⁹¹ & Pinky Bansal⁹²

“Democracy in the contemporary world demands, among other things, an educated and informed people”

One nation one election is a debatable issue and that is the reason Present Prime Minister of India Narendra Modi asked for national debate, public opinion and national survey by resource persons on this issue before implementation of such kind of electoral reform. This paper focuses on the concept of, “ One nation, one election” with the comparative study of countries like South Africa, Belgium, Sweden, Indonesia, etc., on how the concept of simultaneous elections have worked for these countries. One Nation One Election mainly focuses on the process of synchronising the electoral system of both Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies, where the voters will cast vote simultaneously for 2 levels of government Central as well as State. The central objective of this paper is to examine the viability, challenges and implications of synchronised electoral rolls at different levels of government in federal democracies. India, a land where the whole world is considered one family, i.e., “Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam”, the concept of One election is not novel, the same is deep-rooted in Modern Indian history, specifically Post-Independence. In December 2024, the government introduced “The Constitution (One Hundred and twenty ninth amendment) Bill, 2024”, authorizing the Election Commission of India to implement simultaneous elections. India believes in “Unity in Diversity” which points towards the fact that India and Indians believe in Oneness or ‘Unity’ and as a matter of fact India has a Multi-party system which gives the voters the right to choose their leader from diverse choices which signifies ‘Diversity’ in opinions of the public. The analysis finds that

⁹¹ Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

⁹² Student, *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

synchronised elections could cause massive cost savings for both the Center and state government by reducing costs related to election administration, security deployments, and governance disruptions. This paper will also give a brief overview of the historical background of the concept of One Nation One Election and analyses benefits of simultaneous elections with respect to good amount of cost-reduction, time saving as well as how it will affect the governance of India in a good way. Also, limitations and challenges are discussed and with brief suggestions, the paper will be concluded.

UNLOCKING INDIA'S POTENTIAL: THE PROS AND CONS OF 'SIMULTANEOUS ELECTION'

Harsh Raj⁹³ & Prakash Kumar Patel⁹⁴

The proposal of one nation, one election has become a hotspot for debate about federalism structure and cooperative democracy. The idea of this proposal is based on the simultaneous elections to be conducted for both the Parliament and the Legislative Assemblies of the states in order to enhance governance and reduce costs. In the present time, elections are conducted separately, which has resulted in a continuous cycle of elections. Some political parties and civil society are supporting the proposal to reduce costs and let the elected representatives focus on their duty effectively. On the other hand, opposite parties, particularly regional parties, are protesting and criticizing the proposal on the ground that the very concept violates the federal structure of the Constitution and undermines the effectiveness of regional parties. In the first part of the article, the study provides a historical background about the simultaneous elections that were conducted in India. In the middle part of the article, the author discussed the recent development and Constitutional aspects of One Nation One Election along with the in-depth analysis of the election conducted by the different Indian states. In the last part of the article, the study provides a comprehensive analysis of how it benefits India and poses significant

⁹³ Student, *Jamia Milia Islamia, New Delhi.*

⁹⁴ Student, *Jamia Milia Islamia, New Delhi.*

challenges. Before jumping into the conclusion, the author provides some suggestions to avoid the challenges and reinforce the public trust in constitutional democracy while upholding elections simultaneously.

Keywords: *Simultaneous election, Election Commission, Constitutional bill, Law Commission*

DEMOCRATIC ENGAGEMENT IN THE AGE OF ELECTORAL SYNCHRONIZATION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RISKS AND REFORMS

Havish Dhanwantri⁹⁵ & Veni Arora⁹⁶

The recent debate on, “One Nation, One Election” (ONOE) is dominantly framed in terms of administrative efficiency, fiscal savings, reducing voter fatigue and governance stability, but a critical yet underexplored dimension lies in the risks that the concept poses for voter engagement and democratic participation, particularly in context of long political gaps between electoral exercises. Reduction in the number of polls conducted risks creating a democratic engagement gap, where the people are left with fewer opportunities to voice their concerns and hold representatives accountable.

This paper takes a comparative perspective to analyse these risks by using case studies from various countries who have adopted a similar system of electoral exercises, and attempts to answer if there is a pattern of decreased issue-based participation, centralization of social issues and reduced responsiveness to regional issues. By analysing turnout trends, electoral participation and public trust surveys, the paper attempts to answer how the system could impact the electoral process in India, if implemented. The comparative method helps provide a detailed understanding of whether ONOE will deepen disengagement or if supplementary democratic practices could counterbalance these effects.

⁹⁵ Student, *University Institute of Legal Studies, Punjab University.*

⁹⁶ Student, *University Institute of Legal Studies, Punjab University.*

Methodologically the paper will adopt a review-based as well as an empirical approach, drawing on the data from various jurisdictions attempting to establish patterns and investigating common links, if any and analysing secondary data on electoral reforms as well. Thus, the paper will not just review the existing data but will also attempt to establish an understanding around it. The empirical component involves a review of secondary data—such as voter turnout trends, first-time voter participation to assess whether reducing electoral frequency may increase disengagement.

Lastly, the paper will briefly discuss transition strategies, emphasizing phased or hybrid models. Tentative proposals include: (i) staggered synchronization of elections over two cycles, and (ii) leveraging digital participatory platforms to sustain civic engagement between electoral cycles. These strategies are evaluated for their constitutional feasibility and potential to preserve democratic vibrancy.

Keywords: *One Nation One Election, voter engagement, democratic participation, electoral trust, comparative democracy.*

SYNCHRONIZING ELECTIONS IN INDIA: LESSONS FROM HISTORY AND EUROPE FOR TODAY'S POLITICAL LANDSCAPE

Puja⁹⁷ & Radhika Aggarwal⁹⁸

The idea of One Nation One Election first came around immediately after the time of India's independence and remained in place from 1951-1967 after which it began falling out of place as elections started becoming uncoordinated for various reasons, whether it be party splits, or the dissolutions of Assemblies, several complications arose and ever since, the country hasn't seen simultaneous elections across all the states alongside Union elections.

⁹⁷ Student, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.

⁹⁸ Student, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.

After the High-Level Committee on simultaneous elections, headed by former President Ram Nath Kovind, constituted by the Government of India on 2nd September 2023, submitted its report on One Nation One Elections, the discussions started yet again. The Committee received over 21,500 responses, with 80% in favour of simultaneous elections. The responses came from across the country, with the highest responses being from Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Kerala, West Bengal, Gujarat, and Uttar Pradesh.

However where on one hand, business organisations like CII, FICCI, and ASSOCHAM supported the proposal, highlighting the positive impact on economic stability by reducing disruptions and costs associated with election cycles, its conflicting perspectives on social, political, and legal impacts have not been sufficiently addressed. In this paper, we consider the key questions: Will holding simultaneous polls enhance government efficiency while diminishing administrative disruptions? How might they change federal dynamics, voter behaviour, and the competitiveness of Indian elections? What practical, constitutional, and logistical hurdles—such as phased one-time alignment of assembly tenures, the handling of no-confidence motions, and the protection of regional voices—must be addressed?

To situate these discussions, the study takes a global approach, reflecting on some European countries, including Sweden, Germany and Belgium, that are conducting synchronous national and subnational elections. These models illuminate the potential benefits of simultaneous polls, including reduced electoral costs, streamlined governance, greater policy stability, and decreased voter fatigue. At the same time, European experiences warn of challenges such as the dominance of national parties over regional issues and the risk of undermining local representation and pluralism.

While drawing such examples which include the themes like concurrent elections to European Union Parliament and the regional as well as National Elections, the existence of parties and sub-parties, the paper aims to explore different techniques and conditions where the system has been functioning in the present day time and thereby through the analysis of current Indian climate, we compare how India with one of the largest democracies remains with a need to

analyse its religious, caste, topographical diversities before implementation of such models. The study, therefore, advocates a nuanced approach determined by historical experience, constitutional safeguards, and widely comparative global perspectives, emphasising broad political consensus and incremental policy implementation to preserve India's democratic diversity alongside enhanced electoral coherence.

Keywords: *Synchronizing Elections, Comparative study, Centre-State Relations, European electorate system.*

FEASIBILITIES OF SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DEMOCRACIES

Akshat⁹⁹ & Lalit Kumar¹⁰⁰

‘One Nation, One Election’ - The phrase has become an integral part of public discourse in recent times. The topic is being debated in nearly all social and political spheres of society. Simultaneous Elections hold a significant place in the history of the country. When India got its independence from the British Empire and became a Republic, the first four general elections to the Lok Sabha and State Assemblies were conducted in a synchronized manner in 1951-52, 1957, 1962, and 1967. Then came the years 1968 and 1969, due to premature dissolution of some state legislative assemblies including Haryana, by-elections had to be conducted, thereby disrupting the cycle of simultaneous elections. Following that, on December 27th, 1970, Smt. Indira Gandhi, then-PM, called for the dissolution of Lok Sabha fifteen months ahead of its schedule in 1972. The next elections were conducted in 1971, hence, stopping the simultaneous elections till date. The Central Government has brought the issue into limelight again after many decades. The Government of India constituted an 8-member High Level Committee on September 2nd, 2023 under the Chairmanship of Shri Ram Nath Kovind, Former President of India, to discuss the feasibility of conducting simultaneous polls in the country. The Committee worked relentlessly

⁹⁹ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

¹⁰⁰ Student, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University.*

for 191 days and submitted the 18,626- page Report to Hon'ble President of India, Smt. Droupadi Murmu, on March 14th, 2024. The Report highlights that conducting staggered polls cause policy paralysis, burden on the nation's economy, voter fatigue, and administrative mismanagement. In the Report, all the members of the Committee suggested conducting elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies in the first stage and elections to Municipalities and Panchayats in the second stage within 100 days of conducting the first stage. The concept of simultaneous polls is followed in many countries of the world, including Sweden, Indonesia, and Germany, among others. The findings of the report are backed by the examples of more than five countries. This paper analyzes the policies and processes by which these countries are conducting simultaneous elections. This paper also aims to conduct a comparative study as of how the practices can be implemented in India's perspective, thereby, making simultaneous elections, popularly known as 'One Nation, One Election (ONOE)', a successful change.

Keywords: *India, Comparative Analysis, Democracy, Simultaneous Elections.*